

PEDvolution

Interoperable solutions to streamline
PED evolution and cross-sectoral integration

Deliverable 10.1

Plan for Exploitation and Dissemination

**Co-funded by
the European Union**

Schweizerische Eidgenossenschaft
Confédération suisse
Confederazione Svizzera
Confederaziun svizra

Swiss Confederation

Federal Department of Economic Affairs,
Education and Research EAER
**State Secretariat for Education,
Research and Innovation SERI**

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement N° 101138472.

The Swiss project participants received funding from the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SERI).

Document Summary Information

Grant Agreement No	101138472	Acronym	PEDvolution
Full Title	Interoperable solutions to streamline PED evolution and cross-sectoral integration		
Start Date	01/01/2024	Duration	36 months
Project URL	https://www.pedvolution.eu/		
Deliverable	D10.1 - Plan for Exploitation and Dissemination		
Work Package	WP10 - Communication and Dissemination (Year 1)		
Contractual due date	30/06/2024	Actual submission date	28/06/2024 (first submission) 26/2/2026 (resubmission)
Nature	Report	Dissemination Level	Public
Lead Beneficiary	SXS		
Responsible Author	Maria-Ioanna Pavlopoulou, Alexander Deliyannis (SXS)		
Contributions from	Foivos Galatoulas (INLE), Evyatar Littwitz (ESG), Ilia Pietri (ICOM), Katarina Kosutova, Amin Kouti (VITO), Sašo Brus (OFFSET), Alemu Belay (SIN), Matthias Haase (ZHAW)		
Reviewed by	Reda El Makroum (TUW), Markos Psimitis, Marina Laskari (INLE)		

Copyright message

©PEDvolution Consortium 2024. This document comprises entirely original and unreleased content unless explicitly stated otherwise. Recognition of previously published material and the contributions of others has been expressed through suitable citation, quotation, or both. Reproduction is permitted, with acknowledgment of the source.

Disclaimer

PEDvolution - This project has received funding from the Horizon Europe Framework Programme (HORIZON) under the GA No. 101138472. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or CINEA. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them. The European Commission holds no responsibility for any potential utilisation of the information it contains. The information is

D10.1. Plan for Exploitation and Dissemination

presented "as is" with no assurance or warranty, whether explicit or implicit, regarding its suitability for any specific purpose. The user assumes sole responsibility and risk when using this information.

Revision history (including peer reviewing & quality control)

VERSION	ISSUE DATE	% COMPLETE ¹	CHANGES	CONTRIBUTOR(S)
v0.1	11/03/2024	10%	Table of Contents	SXS
v0.2	21/03/2024	10%	Revised Table of Contents	SXS, INLE, TUW
v1.0	22/04/2024	100%	Plan for Exploitation and Dissemination (1 st version for review)	SXS, INLE
v1.1	01/05/2024	100%	1 st round of peer review	TUW, INLE, SXS
v2.0	10/05/2024	100%	Revised deliverable addressing TUW & INLE (IRs) comments. Revisions and additions/clarifications made throughout the document. Added indicate KPIs per year to facilitate monitoring.	SXS
v2.1	16/05/2024	100%	2 nd round of peer review & input provision from WPLs regarding C&D&E objectives per WP.	VITO, SIN, OFFSET, SWW, ICOM, ZHAW, TUW, INLE, SXS
v2.2	23/05/2024	100%	Revised deliverable, addressing IRs comments mainly in Chapter 10, inclusion of input provided by WPLs reading C&D&E objectives per WP and exploitation throughout the document.	SXS, INLE
v2.3	12/06/2024	100%	Addressed additional minor comments by INLE mainly regarding Chapters 7 and 9. Addition of the SWISS funding acknowledgement and reference (Chapter 6).	SXS
v3.0	26/06/2024	100%	Version for submission. Final minor modifications throughout. Addition of Annexes.	SXS

¹ According to Project's Quality Assurance Process

D10.1. Plan for Exploitation and Dissemination

v4.0	31/10/2025	100%	Contributions to standardisation activities of CEN/TC 465 added in Section 9.2.	INLE
-------------	------------	------	---	------

Table of Contents

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	11
1 INTRODUCTION	12
1.1 Mapping the Project’s Outputs.....	12
1.2 Deliverable Overview and Report Structure.....	16
1.3 PEDvolution project scope and background.....	17
1.3.1 Project Overview & Objectives.....	17
1.3.2 Challenges addressed by PEDvolution.....	17
1.3.3 Expected Results and Outputs.....	18
1.3.4 Who is it for?.....	20
1.3.5 PEDvolution Consortium.....	21
2 MAIN OBJECTIVES	22
2.1 Communication, Dissemination & Exploitation objectives.....	22
2.2 Objectives per Work Package.....	24
2.3 Purpose of this plan.....	29
3 COMMUNICATION, DISSEMINATION & EXPLOITATION STRATEGY	30
3.1 Context, Challenges and Means.....	30
3.2 Strategic Approach.....	31
4 TARGET GROUPS	32
5 KEY MESSAGES & MAIN COMMUNICATION ELEMENTS	35
5.1 Key Messages.....	35
5.2 Communication Elements.....	36
5.2.1 Project Name.....	36
5.2.2 Project keywords and catchphrases.....	36
5.2.3 Content directions and wording.....	37
5.2.4 Project vision & identity.....	39
5.2.5 Project spokespersons.....	39
6 COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION TOOLS & CHANNELS	40
6.1 Project Visual Identity and Templates.....	40
6.1.1 Project Logo, colours and basic aesthetics.....	40
6.1.2 Funding Authorities’ logos and disclaimers.....	41
6.1.3 Font sets, Text formation.....	42
6.1.4 Presentation template.....	42
6.1.5 Report/Deliverable template.....	43
6.1.6 Meeting agenda and Minutes template.....	43
6.1.7 Web Design elements.....	43
6.1.8 News Alerts template.....	43
6.1.9 Social media identity headers & avatars.....	43
6.2 Communication Tools: Printable Materials.....	44
6.2.1 Brochure.....	44
6.2.2 Poster.....	44
6.2.3 Roll-up Banner.....	45
6.3 Online communication Channels and Resources.....	46
6.3.1 Social media posts.....	46

D10.1. Plan for Exploitation and Dissemination

6.3.2	Project Website	47
6.3.3	News Alerts	48
6.3.4	GDPR-compliant contacts database	48
6.3.5	Advertorial Video.....	48
6.3.6	Digital presentation.....	49
6.3.7	Digital Gateways –Data Hubs	49
6.4	Communication Matrix	50
7	EXPERT COMMUNICATION & DISSEMINATION ACTIVITIES & networks	51
7.1	3 rd Party Events.....	51
7.2	Final Conference at EU-level.....	54
7.3	The BRIDGE Initiative	55
7.3.1	Purpose and requirements	55
7.3.2	Partners’ roles and expected participation	58
7.3.3	Other EU Initiatives.....	58
8	KEY EXPLOITATION RESULTS (KERs) & EXPLOITATION PATHWAYS	59
8.1	Key Exploitable Results.....	59
8.2	Exploitation Pathways.....	60
9	EXPLOITATION IN MARKET AND POLICY.....	63
9.1	Business Plan and Path to Commercialisation.....	63
9.2	Contribution to Standardisation, Policy, and Regulation	64
9.3	Follow-up plan after the project ends	66
10	COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION WORK PLAN	67
10.1	GANTT Chart.....	67
10.2	Partners’ expected contributions and detailed work plan	68
10.2.1	Partners’ roles and responsibilities	68
10.2.2	Detailed Work Plan WP10-12	73
10.2.3	Official Public Deliverables foreseen within WP10 - 12	76
11	GUIDANCE FOR THE USE OF MEDIA.....	77
12	KEY PERFORMANCE INDICATORS	78
13	MONITORING AND TRACKING	80
13.1	Procedure and Partners’ roles.....	80
14	CONCLUSION	81
15	REFERENCES.....	82
15.1	Definition of basic terms.....	82
15.2	Sources	83
ANNEX I: PROJECT IDENTITY AND APPLICATIONS		84
ANNEX II: PRINTABLE MATERIALS.....		91
ANNEX III: DIGITAL PRESENTATION.....		94
ANNEX IV: TRACKING & MONITORING TOOL.....		95

List of Figures

Figure 1: Process leading to dissemination and exploitation of project results	23
Figure 2: Timeline for dissemination, exploitation, and communication activities	30
Figure 3: Relationship between target groups' expertise and type of body	34
Figure 4: PEDvolution logo with and without tagline	40
Figure 5: EU Co-funding notice	41
Figure 6: SERI logo	41
Figure 7: PEDvolution LinkedIn and Twitter accounts	46
Figure 8: Phases of the PEDvolution liaison and synergies plan	57
Figure 9: PEDvolution Business Model Canvas	63
Figure 11: Planned activities after the end of PEDvolution	66
Figure 12: WP10 - 12 Work Plan Overview	67
Figure 13: PEDvolution detailed work plan for WP10 - 12	75
Figure 14: PEDvolution public deliverables foreseen within WP10 - 12	76

List of Tables

Table 1: Terminology	9
Table 2: Adherence to Project’s GA Deliverable & Tasks Descriptions.....	12
Table 3: PEDvolution expected results per WP	19
Table 4: The PEDvolution Consortium	21
Table 5: Main C&D&E objectives for Technical WPs	24
Table 6: Main C&D&E Objectives for Non-technical WPs.....	27
Table 7: Relevant target groups for C&D&E.....	32
Table 8: PEDvolution target groups vs. EC target audience categories	33
Table 9: Basic content directions for Non-Experts and Expert Groups.....	38
Table 10: Relationship between Target groups and Communication Tools and Channels	50
Table 11: Indicative EU/International 3 rd Party Events	52
Table 12: Indicative National/Regional 3 rd Party Events	53
Table 13: PEDvolution KERs and exploitation pathways.....	60
Table 14: PEDvolution Public Deliverables.....	69
Table 15: Provision of input for the PEDvolution dissemination channels.....	71
Table 16: Partners’ attendance in EU-International 3 rd party events.....	72
Table 17: PEDvolution C&D&E Metrics and Targets & Indicative breakdown per year	78

Glossary of terms and abbreviations

Table 1: Terminology

ABBREVIATION / TERM	DESCRIPTION
AE	Affiliated Entity
AIOTI	Alliance for IoT and Edge Computing Innovation
AP	Associated Partner
BEN	Beneficiary
BMC	Business Model Canvas
C&D&E	Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation
C&D&E Manager	Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Manager
CA	Consortium Agreement
CEN/TC	Technical Committee (TC) of the European Committee for Standardization (CEN)
CINEA	European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency
CMS	Content Management System
COO	Coordinator
EC	European Commission
EO	Expected Outcome
EPBD	Energy Performance of Buildings Directive
ESCOs	Energy service companies
EU	European Union
EUSEW	European Sustainable Energy Week
EWRC	European Week of Regions and Cities
GA	Grant Agreement
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation

D10.1. Plan for Exploitation and Dissemination

ABBREVIATION / TERM	DESCRIPTION
IoT	Internet of Things
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
IPRL	Intellectual Propriety Readiness Level
KER	Key Exploitable Result
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LB	Lead Beneficiary
MRL	Market Readiness Level
NGO	Non-Governmental Organisation
PC	Project Coordinator
PEDs	Positive Energy Districts
PED-EU-NET	Positive Energy Districts European Network
PR	Project Results
R&D	Research and Development
SERI	Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation
SMEs	Small and medium-sized enterprises
SOTA	State-of-the-art
SRL	Societal Readiness Level
TL	Task Leader
TM	Technical Manager
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
WG	Working Group
WP	Work Package
WPL	Work Package Leader

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Project partners should advise the Plan for Exploitation and Dissemination (D10.1) throughout the project duration, as a primary point of reference to guide them in the overall implementation of the communication, dissemination, and exploitation activities (i.e. Work Packages 10, 11, 12).

The document sets out the main objectives of the PEDvolution communication and dissemination activities and provides guidance on how they will be achieved. The plan defines the relevant communication and dissemination channels and tools to be used, including the use of the digital, printed, and social media channels, presents an overview of the target groups and their main characteristics, the KPIs to measure and monitor efficiency of implementation, and provides initial guidelines to encourage the further exploitation and impact of project results after project completion.

This document is dynamic and will be updated as required throughout the project's duration. The deliverable will also be used as a point of reference when developing the communication, and dissemination activities' report at the end of each year (D10.2, D11.1, D12.1), and for the deliverables D11.2 "KERs and characterisation" and D12.1 "PEDvolution replication and market analysis & exploitation strategy", which will detail the exploitation plan of each promising Key Exploitable Result. The contents of this Plan reflect the GA version signed by the EC on 12/12/2023 (with specific reference to Article 17) and the CA (with specific reference to Section 8.4) signed before the GA signature. In case of an amendment to the GA or CA this document will be revised accordingly.

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Mapping the Project's Outputs

The purpose of this section is to map PEDvolution's Grant Agreement (GA) commitments, within the formal deliverable description and the task description, against the project's respective outputs and work performed. The formal deliverable and task descriptions are provided in the 'Project GA Component Title' and 'Project GA Component Outline' columns in [Table 2](#) below. The respective outputs and work performed are described in the 'Justification' column. The chapters where these outputs and work are outlined are indicated in the 'Respective Document Chapter(s)' column.

Table 2: Adherence to Project's GA Deliverable & Tasks Descriptions

PROJECT GA COMPONENT TITLE	PROJECT GA COMPONENT OUTLINE	RESPECTIVE DOCUMENT CHAPTER(S)	JUSTIFICATION
DELIVERABLE			
D10.1: Plan for Exploitation and Dissemination	Plan for Exploitation and Dissemination, incl. Communication (T10.1)	Chapters 1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8, 9,10,11,12,13	The deliverable details all the components required to be defined in the Plan for Exploitation and Dissemination in line with T10.1.
TASKS			
T10.1: Communication tools and activities	This task provides the framework for engaging PEDvolution's audience, ensuring consistent and recognisable communication, a strong online presence and leveraging outreach opportunities.	Chapters 1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8, 9,10,11,12,13	The deliverable serves as the PEDvolution Plan for Exploitation and Dissemination in line with the requirements of ST10.1.1, providing the framework to ensure engagement of target groups and consistent implementation of the project's communication and dissemination activities.
ST10.1.1: Development of communication & dissemination strategy and plan	Development of communication & dissemination strategy and plan, including: main objectives of communication & dissemination activities, overview of target groups and their main characteristics, key messages & main	Chapters 2,3,4,5,6,7,8, 9,10,11,12,13	Chapter 2 presents the C&D&E overall objectives, and the purpose of this plan. Chapter 3 sets out the C&D&E context, means and strategic approach, while Chapter 4 presents the target groups and their main classification. Chapter 5 focuses on the project's key messages and communication

D10.1. Plan for Exploitation and Dissemination

PROJECT GA COMPONENT TITLE	PROJECT GA COMPONENT OUTLINE	RESPECTIVE DOCUMENT CHAPTER(S)	JUSTIFICATION
	<p>communication elements, relevant communication & dissemination channels & tools, links between groups, channels & tools, KPIs to measure & monitor efficiency of implementation, overall guidance for the use of digital, printed, and social media, initial table of activities & relevant events.</p>		<p>elements, including the project keywords, vision and symbolism.</p> <p>Chapter 7 deals with expert communication & dissemination activities including 3rd party events participation (including tables with indicative events), the final PEDvolution conference and the collaboration with the BRIDGE and other EU initiatives.</p> <p>Chapter 8 presents the KERs and exploitation pathways, while Chapter 9 deals with the concept of exploitation in market and policy as well as project sustainability.</p> <p>Chapter 10 details the work plan related with Work Packages 10, 11 & 12, as well as partners' roles and expected contributions.</p> <p>Chapter 11 presents guidelines for the use of media to be considered by partners and Chapter 12 summarises the C&D&E Key Performance Indicators to be used for monitoring efficient implementation.</p> <p>Finally, Chapter 13, explains the need for monitoring and tracking of C&D&E activities and presents guidelines for partners on how and when to use the tracking tool.</p>
<p>ST10.1.2: Development of project identity, applications and basic documentation</p>	<p>Development of project identity, applications and basic documentation. A consistent visual identity will be designed for all material to be publicly disseminated and available for all WPs to use. Applications will include: PowerPoint template, template for reports, digital News Alert and website headers, social media identity</p>	<p>Chapters 5, 6</p>	<p>Chapter 5 focuses on the project's key messages and communication elements, including the project keywords, vision and symbolism.</p> <p>Chapter 6 analyses the PEDvolution communication and dissemination tools and channels, to be used during the project duration including i) the project's visual identity and templates (incl. PowerPoint template, template for reports) ii) printable materials (incl. poster, brochure, roll-up banner) and iii) online communication channels and</p>

D10.1. Plan for Exploitation and Dissemination

PROJECT GA COMPONENT TITLE	PROJECT GA COMPONENT OUTLINE	RESPECTIVE DOCUMENT CHAPTER(S)	JUSTIFICATION
	<p>headers and avatars. Documentation to present the project at relevant opportunities will include: factsheet and slides in English, project brochure, poster and roll-up banner in all project languages (6+1).</p>		<p>resources (incl. project website, social media, news alerts, digital gateways). The chapter also includes a matrix presenting the link between Target groups and Communication Tools and Channels.</p>
<p>ST10.1.3: Project online presence</p>	<p>Project online presence (website, hubs, social). The PEDvolution project website will be set up on a modern Content Management System (CMS) with a responsive design, allowing quick updates, integration of external material, interactivity, and rapid search/access to the content. Visitors will be able to subscribe to News Alerts and download public material. Public deliverables and project announcements will also be posted to BUILD UP & Construction 21 as relevant data hubs. PEDvolution accounts in Twitter, LinkedIn and YouTube will promote project results and engage with interested stakeholders. Project partners will be asked to use their own accounts to further replicate posts. Twitter and YouTube feeds will be embedded on the project website.</p>	<p>Chapter 6</p>	<p>Chapter 6 analyses the PEDvolution communication and dissemination tools to be implemented during the project duration. Section 6.3 specifically addresses the online communication channels and resources i.e. project website, social media accounts (LinkedIn, Twitter, YouTube, News Alerts, digital gateways and hubs).</p>

D10.1. Plan for Exploitation and Dissemination

PROJECT GA COMPONENT TITLE	PROJECT GA COMPONENT OUTLINE	RESPECTIVE DOCUMENT CHAPTER(S)	JUSTIFICATION
<p>T10.2: Liaison with BRIDGE and other EU initiatives</p>	<p>This task performs the liaison with other projects and consortia, the BRIDGE initiative, AIOTI, Annex 83, COST Action on PEDS, as well as with interoperability and standardisation initiatives and national/international bodies (InterConnect, FlexCommunity.eu, etc.). Early networking activities will serve to take advantage from running initiatives' results, regarding exploitation and replication potential. Inputs will be used in the co-design PED-RA as well as the other PEDvolution solutions. These activities will continue in T11.3 and T12.2. As soon as the project has been awarded INLE will contact the BRIDGE secretariat specifying the activities and the fields of interests for the cooperation with the BRIDGE initiative. In Year 1 of the project, PEDvolution will have already participated in the annual general assembly of BRIDGE and identified possible synergies with the Working Groups that project partners are already members of.</p>	<p>Chapter 7</p>	<p>Chapter 7 analytically presents, the foreseen participation in 3rd party events, as well the purpose and partners' roles regarding liaison with the BRIDGE and other relevant EU initiatives and consortia.</p>

1.2 Deliverable Overview and Report Structure

This report serves as the project's Plan for Exploitation and Dissemination and should be used as a reference point by all partners throughout the project duration, as regards the implementation of the communication and dissemination activities. It provides the framework for engaging PEDvolution's audience, ensuring consistent and recognisable communication with target groups, a strong online presence and leveraging outreach opportunities.

The deliverable is structured as follows:

- **Chapter 1:** Introduces the scope of this report and presents an overview of the project;
- **Chapter 2:** Defines the project's overall C&D&E objectives, the purpose of this plan and specific goals per Work Package;
- **Chapter 3:** Sets out the C&D&E context, means and strategic approach;
- **Chapter 4:** Presents the target groups, their classification, main characteristics and relevance to communication, dissemination, and exploitation activities;
- **Chapter 5:** Introduces the project's key messages and communication elements, including the project's vision, and symbolism;
- **Chapter 6:** Describes the communication and dissemination tools to be developed including the project's visual identity and templates, printable materials and online communication channels and resources;
- **Chapter 7:** Deals with expert communication & dissemination activities (3rd party events participation, the final PEDvolution conference and the collaboration with other EU initiatives);
- **Chapter 8:** Considers the KERs and potential exploitation pathways;
- **Chapter 9:** Deals with the concept of exploitation in market and policy as well as project sustainability;
- **Chapter 10:** Details the work plan related with communication and dissemination activities, as well as partners' roles and expected contributions;
- **Chapter 11:** Includes guidelines for the use of media to be considered by partners;
- **Chapter 12:** Presents the C&D&E KPIs and defines an indicative breakdown for each KPI per year;
- **Chapter 13:** Explains the need for monitoring and tracking of C&D&E activities and presents guidelines for partners the use of the tracking tool;
- **Annex I:** Project Identity and applications;
- **Annex II:** Printable materials;
- **Annex III:** Digital presentation;
- **Annex IV:** Tracking & Monitoring tool.

1.3 PEDvolution project scope and background

This section presents an overview of the PEDvolution project, its main objectives and expected results. Its purpose is to set the scene and introduce the project's scope before presenting the communication and dissemination strategy.

1.3.1 Project Overview & Objectives

PEDvolution paves the way for cross-sectoral integration of ever-evolving Positive Energy Districts (PEDs). The project consists of three consecutive phases namely, analyse, co-develop, and demonstrate; during which European pioneers in PED conceptualisation, implementation and tool development will co-develop and implement seven interoperable solutions accommodating the constant evolution of PEDs.

The PEDvolution solutions will evaluate and improve the 'PED Readiness Level' according to the four genes of the PED genotype: social, technology, interoperability, and market (See [Chapter 15](#)). These are influenced by their interaction within the PED and its environment (PED phenotype - See [Chapter 15](#)).

The aim is for the PEDvolution solutions to enable PEDs to evolve and adapt in a changing and challenging environment, protecting their citizens, delivering products and services of the highest quality, and thus supporting Europe to gain power in the global energy competition, while preserving its values and socio-economic way of life. The developed solutions will be demonstrated, tested and validated in at least six real-life PEDs across Europe, paving the way for replication, upscaling, and mainstreaming.

Overall, the project contributes towards addressing the following specific needs:

1. Improve energy efficiency coupled with better integration of local renewables and local excess heat sources within the districts.
2. Increase citizen participation and integration of consumers and energy communities in the value chain of the energy system.
3. Improve cross-sectoral integration on energy and non-energy sectors within PEDs (between buildings, the users and the regional energy, mobility, and ICT systems).
4. Demonstrate fully interoperable solutions for planning, design, development, and management of PEDs.

1.3.2 Challenges addressed by PEDvolution

PEDvolution seeks to contribute towards Europe's wider goal to a climate-neutral society by 2050, by working towards decarbonising the urban environment. With an estimated 97% of dwellings not fit for purpose, a clean energy system and a just transition require more than isolated technological solutions for individual buildings.

Consequently, it is crucial to implement fully interoperable solutions at the neighbourhood level, that can improve energy efficiency as well as integrate local renewables and excess heat sources more effectively, rather than to approach each building separately. Such a community-driven approach empowers citizens to collectively interact and integrate with the regional energy, mobility, and ICT systems, while addressing social innovation. Still, a common misconception is that PEDs are a means to an end. Yet, an urban energy transition is in constant evolution, due to continuous changes in the

environment such as evolving social context, new urban development, adapted legislation, the introduction of novel technologies, increased electric vehicles and thus storage capacity.

As such, there is a strong analogy with the theory of evolution. If an environment changes the traits that enhance “survival” will also gradually change or evolve. Although the DNA between PEDs varies, the implementation and evolution of different PEDs is not a process of chance since the environment determines the probability of success in the urban energy transition. PEDvolution aims to contribute towards addressing this challenge, by developing tools and solutions which will assist and encourage the planning, design, and development of PEDs.

1.3.3 Expected Results and Outputs

PEDvolution aims to develop the following 7 interoperable solutions:

1. **PED Design and Planning Toolset:** A Digital Twin planning tool to empower developers and managers to accelerate district development pathways towards achieving or further evolving a PED. The tool will provide accurate energy models of buildings and district assets as a basis to generate renovation pathways along district heating/cooling grids based on local conditions.
2. **PED Readiness Assessment:** A systematic process of monitoring and determining the performance of a neighbourhood or district, in relation to the essential characteristics of a Positive Energy District.
3. **Dynamic Decision Support Guideline for PED Development:** Targeted guidelines and efficient workflow for PED development decisions related to the choice of technologies and strategies with respect to urban planning, energy efficiency and integration of local renewable energy sources.
4. **PED Energy Manager:** Multi-level toolset for efficient management of energy processes within PEDs. Controls energy processes in residential and non-residential environments, assesses and extracts flexibility, optimises the operation in multi-sector environments and exploits flexibility on several energy and flexibility markets.
5. **Data Exchange, Integration, and Interoperability Platform:** The PEDvolution interoperability platform will comprise the digital backbone of the PEDvolution approach, providing a central node for trustworthy exchange of data, access to sophisticated PED design, planning, management and flexibility tools, thus enabling effective sector integration targeted to a multitude of energy and non-energy carriers (for instance, mobility and water). The goal will be to unify energy node information flows by pursuing a digital integration strategy for all relevant energy data, district infrastructure and service models.
6. **PED Business Models:** A set of building blocks, known as ‘business model patterns,’ that have been proven successful in community-based business solutions. The tool’s process will show PEDs how to adapt business model patterns to the local context and combine them to create promising business models. A set of building blocks, known as ‘business model patterns,’ that have been proven successful in community-based business solutions. The tool’s process will show PEDs how to adapt business model patterns to the local context and combine them to create promising business models.
7. **PED Social Innovation tool:** A methodology that allows users to assess the state of the community and to understand the priorities, values and views of different stakeholders or actors to design an energy solution or related activities to be compatible with local needs. The aim is to contribute to long lasting adoption of planned or existing energy innovation in a PED.

D10.1. Plan for Exploitation and Dissemination

The project's expected outcomes can be summarised as follows:

1. Increased availability of tools, guides and interoperable solutions for planning, design, development, and management of PEDs.
2. Improved integration of energy (e.g. distributed renewable energy generation, waste heat utilisation, storage) and non-energy sectors (e.g. mobility) within PEDs.
3. Improved integration of PEDs in energy systems and improved contribution of PEDs to energy grid robustness regarding dependencies to energy supplies.
4. Increased social entrepreneurship and citizen participation and engagement in energy communities.
5. Increased participation of consumers and energy communities in the value chain of the energy system.

PEDvolution's expected results, foreseen to be achieved during project implementation within the scope of specific Work Packages (WP) are summarised in the below table:

Table 3: PEDvolution expected results per WP

RESULT NO.	EXPECTED RESULT	WP
R1	Comprehensive set of user requirements and use cases for the PED solutions	WP1: User-centered system analysis
R2	Local community analysis and initial engagement plan	
R3	Reference system architecture	
R4	Methodology to integrate uncertainty and robustness in PEDs planning and design	WP2: Solution specification and concept design/ WP3: PED design and planning toolset
R5	Methodology for assessing requirements of centralised heating/cooling systems in new and existing PEDs	
R6	Cohesive toolchain for integrated modelling of PED via Digital Twin	
R7	User interface for PED design and management Energy System Asset Management Solutions	WP5: PED Energy Manager
R8	PED Energy Manager, Sector coupling and flexibility Exchange	
R9	Heat Flexibility Manager	
R10	Data exchange, integration and interoperability platform	WP7: Data Exchange, Integration and Interoperability Platform
R11	Energy market mechanisms	
R12	PED readiness assessment framework	WP4: PED Readiness Assessment
R13	Dynamic decision support guideline application	
R14	Package of measures implemented based on the PEDvolution solutions	WP8: Co-developer PEDs preparation and tools integration/
R15	Deployment plans for PEDvolution technologies	
R16	Demonstrator Factsheets	

D10.1. Plan for Exploitation and Dissemination

RESULT NO.	EXPECTED RESULT	WP
		WP9: PEDvolution demonstrators and performance assessment
R17	Business model tools for interoperable PEDs	WP2: Solution specification and concept design/ WP6: PED Business & social innovation tools/ WP9: PEDvolution demonstrators and performance assessment
R18	Social innovation and engagement tools for PEDs	
R19	Plan for Exploitation and Dissemination	WP10: Communication and Dissemination (Year 1)/ WP12: Project Communication, Dissemination and further Exploitation (Year 3)
R20	Report on Liaison with the BRIDGE initiative	

1.3.4 Who is it for?

PEDvolution targets a wide audience, primarily focusing on the following groups (further analysed in [Chapter 4](#)):

- ❖ Energy service providers (ESCOs) & Mobility service providers
- ❖ Residents / Energy consumers / End users
- ❖ Energy prosumers
- ❖ PED developers and managers
- ❖ Research and academic institutes
- ❖ PED investors (i.e. banks, real estate developers and owners, regional funders)
- ❖ Local Authorities and City Planners
- ❖ Policy makers
- ❖ Standardisation bodies
- ❖ Specialist media
- ❖ General public

1.3.5 PEDvolution Consortium

The project brings together the following 15 organisations from 7 European countries, (including public, private and research institutions) presented in [Table 4](#).

Table 4: The PEDvolution Consortium

NO.	PARTICIPANT	ABBREVIATION	TYPE	COUNTRY	C&D&E RELATED ROLE
1	INLECOM INNOVATION ASTIKI MI KERDOSKOPIKI ETAIREIA	INLE	COO	Greece	Project Coordinator/Technical Manager/IPR Manager/ Liaison with BRIDGE and EU initiatives – Task Leader
2	VLAAMSE INSTELLING VOOR TECHNOLOGISCH ONDERZOEK N.V.	VITO	BEN	Belgium	WP2 & WP3 Leader /Solution Provider
3	SMART INNOVATION NORWAY AS	SIN	BEN	Norway	WP6 Leader/Solution Provider
4	NORGES TEKNISK-NATURVUTENSKAPELIGE UNIVERSITET NTNU	NTNU	BEN	Norway	Solution Provider
5	SYMPRAXIS TEAM P.C.	SXS	BEN	Greece	C&D&E Manager
6	OFFSET ENERGY ENERGETSKE RESITVE DOO	OFFSET (formerly RENN)	BEN	Slovenia	WP5 Leader/Solution Provider
7	SWW WUNSIEDEL GMBH	SWW	BEN	Germany	WP9 Leader/PED Manager
8	ES-GEHT!-ENERGIESYSTEME GMBH	ESG	BEN	Germany	WP8 Leader/PED Manager
9	TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITAET WIEN	TUW	BEN	Austria	Solution Provider/Responsible for replication and market analysis
10	INTRACOM SA TELECOM SOLUTIONS	ICOM	BEN	Greece	WP1 & WP7 Leader/Solution Provider
11	ELEKTRO GORENJSKA PODJETJE ZA DISTRIBUCIJO ELEKTRICNE ENERGIJE DD	EG	BEN	Slovenia	PED Manager
11.1	GORENJSKE ELEKTRARNE PROIZVODNJA ELEKTRIKE DOO	GEK	AE	Slovenia	PED Manager
12	ZUKUNFTSENERGIE NORDOSTBAYERN GMBH	ZENOB	BEN	Germany	PED Manager
13	ZURCHER HOCHSCHULE FUR ANGEWANDTE WISSENSCHAFTEN	ZHAW	AP	Switzerland	WP4 Leader/Solution Provider
14	STADT WINTERTHUR	WIN	AP	Switzerland	PED Manager

2 MAIN OBJECTIVES

This chapter defines basic terms, identifies the project's overall communication, dissemination and exploitation (C&D&E) objectives, the specific C&D&E objectives per WP which the partnership should work towards and this plan's objectives.

2.1 Communication, Dissemination & Exploitation objectives

Communication, dissemination, and exploitation are vital concepts for the project.

Communication is a process starting at the beginning of the project and continuing throughout its lifetime. It aims at increasing public awareness, visibility and promoting its activities and results, as well as the engagement and participation of stakeholders and the adoption of the project results by authorities and organisations. It may use simple and accessible language and information through channels such as TV, radio, print, websites and social media.

The project's communication objectives are to:

- ❖ Raise public awareness and improve understanding about the potential of PEDs and their significant contribution towards achieving energy-efficient and sustainable buildings and districts.
- ❖ Inform and raise public awareness about the project, its expected results, and progress.
- ❖ Empower a positive opinion about the project on an EU-level to the wider public.

Dissemination and exploitation concern the diffusion and further utilisation of results and are expected to take place once project results are available, i.e. during the 2nd and 3rd years of project implementation and beyond.

Dissemination relates to the disclosure of the project's results, mostly to audiences such as project stakeholders, professional and scientific communities, policymakers, etc., finally supporting their exploitation. It usually uses more scientific language and information, as well as suitable channels, such as industry or scientific media, websites and events, targeted e-mails, news alerts, and newsletters.

Exploitation is defined as the use of results in further research and innovation activities other than those covered by the action concerned. Such cases include commercial exploitation such as developing, creating, manufacturing, and marketing a product or process, creating and providing a service, or standardisation activities.

The project's dissemination and exploitation objectives are to:

- ❖ Ensure the engagement and participation of stakeholders.
- ❖ Promote the adoption of the project's platform, tools, and solutions by the professional and scientific communities, as well as by the competent national authorities and agencies at the EU -level.
- ❖ Support the dissemination of the project's development.
- ❖ Pave the way for a successful commercial and non-commercial exploitation of the project outcomes.
- ❖ Encourage the dissemination and further exploitation of project results beyond its completion.

Key performance indicators are used to measure the performance of these objectives (see [Chapter 12](#)).

D10.1. Plan for Exploitation and Dissemination

[Figure 1](#) below presents the process that leads to the dissemination and exploitation of project results and outputs. The 1st step “Awareness, Value” involves raising awareness about the project topic, goals and objectives to the project’s target groups. All project partners will contribute to this step through the communication and dissemination activities described in the following Chapters. Steps 2 and 3 “Decision, Action” and “Plus” respectively, concern the project’s dissemination activities and exploitation of project results from targeted groups such as policy makers, PEDs investors and local authorities. All partners will contribute to the dissemination of project results and as regards further dissemination and exploitation primarily, PED Solution Providers will contribute towards this goal.

Figure 1: Process leading to dissemination and exploitation of project results

2.2 Objectives per Work Package

The main communication, dissemination and exploitation objectives per Work Package are presented in [Table 5](#) and [Table 6](#) below. Their purpose is to specify how each relevant WP will contribute towards the achievement of the project's overall C&D&E objectives, by setting precise goals which partners should work towards.

Table 5: Main C&D&E objectives for Technical WPs

WP	TITLE	MAIN C&D&E OBJECTIVE(S)	WP LEADER
1	User-centered system analysis	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Communicate stakeholder analysis and engagement plan for local society and end users of the solutions developed within the project enabling improved understanding of project scope and contributing to stakeholder engagement. - Identify and promote the Super PED concept. - Provide a comprehensive analysis of functional and non-functional requirements for PEDvolution solutions to match the need of stakeholders. - Communicate a comprehensive description of the Use-cases of the project enabling improved understanding of project scope and collaboration with other initiatives. - Expose PEDvolution's architecture (high-level) fostering collaboration with other initiatives. 	ICOM
2	Solution specification and concept design	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Identify key challenges and opportunities for PED planning, design, development, and management and the capture of social, market, technological, interoperability aspects in PEDs. - Identify methodologies and tools for PED assessment and integrated modelling of PEDs via Digital Twins that incorporate a bottom-up energy model of the district. - Identify State-of-the-art (SOTA) related to innovative business models that will enable PED developers, consumers, energy communities and managers to valorise the energy generated by PED assets, exploring the potential of energy market participation, demand response services, carbon credits, and other revenue streams. 	VITO
3	PED design and planning toolset	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Pathways along district heating/cooling grids based on local conditions. - Uncertainty propagation to reduce planning risks and to enhance robustness of PEDs. - Facilitate informed decision-making by providing evidence-based insights to PED developers and managers. 	VITO
4	PED Readiness Assessment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Conduct a strategic plan that outlines how a European harmonised PED readiness assessment can be achieved. The roadmap will include a concrete action plan, identify the priority actions for the European Commission and suggestions for synergies with existing EU and international initiatives. 	

D10.1. Plan for Exploitation and Dissemination

WP	TITLE	MAIN C&D&E OBJECTIVE(S)	WP LEADER
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Determine the detailed requirements and characteristics for the Dynamic Decision Support Guideline, following the ideation phase under WP2 "Solution specification and concept design", proceeding the analysis under WP1 "User-centered system analysis". - Develop an action plan for testing the guideline in the PED demonstrators to ensure successful implementation and deployment. 	ZHAW
5	PED Energy Manager	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Communication of specific benefits stemming from the dynamic operation (control) of the assets - Identification of additional benefits due to sector-coupled operation. - Synergies between different stakeholders (sellers and buyers of flexibility in multiple sectors). - Contribution to standardisation – linking with FlexOffer community. - Techno-socio-economic benefits for PEDs. 	OFFSET (formerly RENN)
6	PED Business & Social Innovation Tools	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Start the implementation of the locally customised tools, by actively engaging and interacting with PEDs, local stakeholders, and technology and Solution Providers through human-centred, participatory processes. - Implementation of the business model innovation tool which is developed and adapted for PEDs with active involvement of all PEDs, tools and technology developers. Various business model options will be provided for each PED through a series of workshops. In a co-development process, all pains and gains of PEDs will be considered for better exploitation of the values proposed by PEDvolution. - Implementation of the PED social innovation tool in the three PED demonstration sites. - WP6 exploitation is connected with the project C&D. Thus, the key exploitable results from the business model and social innovation activities will be validated and presented in the subsequent exploitation activities. - In year 1, communicate and reach out the extend network including the clusters through social medias such as LinkedIn and SIN website and promote the progress of the project and WP6. - In Year 2 and Year 3 publications are foreseen. 	SIN
7	Data Exchange, Integration and Interoperability Platform	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Communication of a common information model covering PEDvolution's ecosystem needs in the energy domain, fostering improved interoperability among PED projects. - Expose the middleware framework of PEDvolution's enabling seamless integration and fostering collaboration with EU Data Spaces. - Communicate extended market trading mechanisms (i.e. FlexOffer) for supporting multi-vector energy trading, contributing to FlexOffer community. 	ICOM

D10.1. Plan for Exploitation and Dissemination

WP	TITLE	MAIN C&D&E OBJECTIVE(S)	WP LEADER
8	Co-developer PEDs preparation and tools integration	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Enable the engagement between PED environments and the 7 PEDvolution solutions and start their integration and implementation. - Launch a call for additional PEDs, so to expand the variety of the PED contexts addressed. - Analyse potential commercial applications for the solutions of PEDvolution. - Develop sustainable business models (while addressing scalability). - Foster innovative ecosystems for the PEDvolution solutions. - Hold co-creation workshops with stakeholders and attend conventions. - Present PEDvolution solutions/project in public energy fairs. - Train communities to use the PEDvolution solutions for collaboration opportunities. 	ESG
9	PEDvolution demonstrators and performance assessment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Efficient demonstration and evaluation of the PEDvolution solutions by the Co-Developer Pilots to the additional demonstrator sites identified in T8.3 "Call for demonstrators", as regards the technical aspects, the smooth running of the implementation of the PEDvolution solutions – technology, business models and social innovation tools included, the ongoing assessment and improvement of the tools, and the initiation of replication activities with external participants. - Develop sustainable business models (while addressing scalability). - Engage stakeholders for collaboration and adoption of the PEDvolution solutions. 	SWW

Table 6: Main C&D&E Objectives for Non-technical WPs

WP	TITLE	MAIN C&D&E OBJECTIVE(S)	WP LEADER
10	Communication and Dissemination (Year 1)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Establish the foundations and first communication and dissemination activities. - Define the Communications and Dissemination strategy. - Identify and provide key channels to reach the main target groups. - Support a strong presence of the project, online and on-location. - Provide the main communication and dissemination tools. - Link the project to key EU-level initiatives. 	SXS
11	Project Communication, Dissemination and further Exploitation (Year 2)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Implementation of the C&D&E activities (continued from year 1) by actively engaging and interacting with PEDs and technology and Solution Providers. - All adapted and customised tools, methods and solutions implemented and tested with respective use cases of the project. - Characterisation of the project's Key Exploitable Results (KERs) to maximise exploitation. 	SXS
12	Project Communication, Dissemination and further Exploitation (Year 3)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Implementation of the C&D&E activities (continued from year 2) - Maximise the exploitation of the PEDvolution and achieve expected impacts during and after the project ends. - Expedite a successful uptake of PEDvolution results, as well as facilitate active involvement and interaction of stakeholders, end users, general public, and actors through the PEDvolution agile communication and dissemination activities. - Execute benchmarking, barriers study and liaison activities, to leverage and capitalize the learnings and experiences from best performers both from PEDvolution PEDs (at different evolution stages) and external PEDs in EU and beyond. - Develop an exploitation plan, do qualification activities and replication and market analysis to define exploitation strategy. - Contribute, upon invitation by the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA), to common information and dissemination activities to increase the visibility and synergies between Horizon Europe supported actions. 	SXS
13	Project Coordination and Management (Year 1)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Communicate the initiation of the project to relevant projects and EU initiatives (Kick-Off meeting, relevant meetings). - Highlight profiles and roles in the project early on. - Inform on the vision, mission, objectives and expected results project. - Organise General Assembly meetings, demo visits, and workshops with PEDS to promote the project. 	INLE

D10.1. Plan for Exploitation and Dissemination

WP	TITLE	MAIN C&D&E OBJECTIVE(S)	WP LEADER
14	Project Coordination and Management (Year 2)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Implementation of the C&D&E activities (continued from year 1). - Promotion of the Open call for additional PEDs, so to expand the variety of the PED contexts addressed. - Organise General Assembly meetings, demo visits, and workshops with PEDS to promote the project. 	INLE
15	Project Coordination and Management (Year 3)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Implementation of the C&D&E activities (continued from year 2). - Promotion of the PEDvolution final conference in Brussels. 	INLE

2.3 Purpose of this plan

This plan is addressed to PEDvolution partners and describes the project's external communication, and dissemination strategy. It supports the effective planning and coordination of all communication tools and channels and provides a plan of the project's communication, dissemination and exploitation activities. The plan defines and guides the development, monitoring and reporting of the dissemination materials and activities.

Its main objective is to encourage the active participation of project partners, stakeholders and 3rd parties in project activities, ensure the diffusion of project results, thereby contributing to its overall success, impact and sustainability.

Concretely, this plan aims to outline the:

- ❖ Project's communication, dissemination and exploitation objectives
- ❖ Identification of target groups and their main characteristics
- ❖ Project's key messages
- ❖ Project logo and catchphrases
- ❖ Overall project identity and the basic communication elements
- ❖ Communication tools & channels to be used
- ❖ Dissemination events and activities
- ❖ Matrices, describing the connection between different groups and objectives, groups and channels, and tools and channels, according to their different characteristics and needs
- ❖ Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) to be used to measure the efficiency and impact of the communication implementation
- ❖ Allocation of work to the PEDvolution project partners and their overall responsibilities
- ❖ Monitoring & Tracking tool

3 COMMUNICATION, DISSEMINATION & EXPLOITATION STRATEGY

3.1 Context, Challenges and Means

PEDvolution’s strategy for communication, dissemination and exploitation of project results is integral in its overall implementation, as several of the solutions to be developed.

This section presents an overview of the crosscutting activities along the project timeline in support of its communication and networking, and the dissemination, exploitation, and replication of the project results by 3rd parties.

The activities are facilitated by SXS as the Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Manager (C&D&E Manager) and supported by TUW as regards the “Replication and Market analysis” (under [Subtask 12.3.2](#)) and by INLE for the “Liaison with [BRIDGE](#) and other EU initiatives” (under tasks T10.2, T11.3 and T12.2) and Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) management.

All partners, particularly PED Managers and Solution Providers, will be involved in their implementation for proper uptake and maximisation of impacts, in line with their foreseen roles in the technical Work Packages. The steps and overall timeline of activities in the three project phases is presented in [Figure 2](#) below. Partners’ roles and responsibilities are detailed in [Section 10.2.1](#).

Figure 2: Timeline for dissemination, exploitation, and communication activities

3.2 Strategic Approach

A strategic client-centric approach to the communication of the project, dissemination of results to – and their exploitation in collaboration with – relevant organisations, is to be implemented across PEDvolution. The aim is to build and maintain a relationship with the organisations which are to make use of the project outcomes, while using awareness of the project itself in a supportive role.

A key factor contributing to effective communication and dissemination is consistency, both in content and in form:

- ❖ The development of any integrated project identity will support implementation of this C&D&E plan, which provides reference elements such as logo, tagline, key visual(s), keywords and guidelines and templates for employing the identity, to ensure positive recognisability of the project, in all appearances and mentions (see [Section 6.1](#)).
- ❖ Consistency in C&D&E will also be ensured through the integrated management of project outreach contacts, through a centralised GDPR-compliant contacts database (see [Section 6.3.4](#)). Similarly, the project website (see [Section 6.3.2](#)) will provide a permanent reference point for all information related to the project, including basic documentation, announcements, video, registration for updates, link to social media and other PEDvolution presence in external sites and resources, interaction with the project partnership network, access to public deliverables.

The following chapters analytically present the work to be implemented, including overview of target groups, key messages, and available communication channels and tools, strategy. Guidance for the use of digital, social, printed materials by the project is provided, and KPIs are also defined.

4 TARGET GROUPS

PEDvolution's audience addresses a wide range of target groups and stakeholders, with different characteristics and needs, thus requiring different strategies, tools, and channels, to achieve maximum impact.

In reaching out to its target groups, the PEDvolution consortium seeks to actively build a relationship with them, starting from initial awareness, facilitating engagement and network development, and possibly leading to advocacy and support of the PEDvolution project's insights and proposal.

The following table presents an overview of the PEDvolution target groups, motivation for engagement and the main content focus and relevance to communication, dissemination, and exploitation.

Table 7: Relevant target groups for C&D&E

TARGET GROUP (TG)	CLASSIFICATION	INTENTION	CONTEXT	C	D	E
TG1: Energy service providers, (ESCOs) & Mobility service providers	Industry / Investors	Intermediaries with the market development and demand-side customers; manage customer satisfaction.	Data exchange, integration and interoperability platform (enabling market participation)	X	X	X
TG2: Residents/ Energy consumers /End users	General Public / Civil Society / Customers	Citizens as experts of their daily environment, activating local inferred knowledge and experience to find opportunities for change.	Business model and social innovation tools	X	X	
TG3: Energy prosumers	General Public / Civil Society / Customers / Investors	Prosumers may contribute to the energy system by offering demand flexibility.	Data exchange, integration and interoperability platform / PED Management Tools (from micro to meso scale)	X	X	X
TG4: PED developers and managers	Industry / Policy Makers / Civil Society	Guide communities and optimise assets at a household, community or grid level.	Data exchange, integration and interoperability platform / PED Management Tools (from micro to meso scale)	X	X	X
TG5: PED Investors (banks, real estate developers, regional funders, etc.)	Investors / Industry / Policy Makers	Categorise viable opportunities to create value and reduce risk; revalue externalities to finance innovations.	PED design and planning toolset / PED energy asset manager / Business model innovation tool	X	X	X
TG6: Local Authorities and City planners	Policy Makers	Usual owners of issues and at the same time Solution Providers; Help to encourage, accelerate, and embrace innovations.	Standardisation/certification of PEDs / Business model and social innovation tools	X	X	X
TG7: Policy makers	Policy Makers/Industry/ Scientific Community	Collaborators and/or recipients of policy and other development activities	Addressing EU policy priorities & global challenges through R&I	X	X	X
TG8: Standardisation bodies	Policy Makers / Industry / Scientific Community	Foster convergence towards global solutions across domains.	PEDvolution Readiness Assessment framework	X	X	X
TG9: Research / Academia	Scientific Community	Catalysts for greater elaboration and adoption.	All of the above (public elements)	X	X	
TG10: Specialist Media	Media	Catalysts for greater awareness and adoption.	All of the above (public elements)	X	X	
TG11: General Public	General Public	The general public can play a crucial role in the overall awareness and impact.	All of the above (public elements)	X	X	

D10.1. Plan for Exploitation and Dissemination

The above target groups can be clustered into the following **four main categories**:

❖ **SUPPLY SIDE**

- Energy service providers, (ESCOs) & Mobility service providers
- Energy prosumers
- PED developers and managers
- Local authorities and city planners

❖ **DEMAND SIDE**

- Residents/ Energy consumers /End users
- Energy prosumers

❖ **FINANCIAL SIDE**

- PED Investors (banks, real estate developers, regional funders)

❖ **PUBLIC SIDE**

- Policy makers
- Energy prosumers
- Standardisation bodies
- Research/Academia, in particular, university departments connected to energy efficiency in buildings
- Local authorities
- Specialist Media with a focus on energy efficiency of buildings and construction
- General public

It is also important to classify the target groups in terms of the target audience categories, as recognised by the Horizon Europe Programme.

Table 8: PEDvolution target groups vs. EC target audience categories

PEDVOLUTION TARGET GROUPS	EC PORTAL TARGET AUDIENCE(S)
Energy service providers (ESCOs)	Industry, Business Partners/Investors
Mobility service providers	Industry, Business Partners/Investors
Residents/ Energy consumers /End users	Citizens/Civil Society
Energy prosumers, end users	Citizens/Civil Society/Investors
PED developers and managers	Industry, Business Partners/Investors
PED Investors (banks, real estate developers, regional funders, etc.)	Investors
Local Authorities and City planners	Regional Authorities/Local authorities

D10.1. Plan for Exploitation and Dissemination

PEDVOLUTION TARGET GROUPS	EC PORTAL TARGET AUDIENCE(S)
Policy makers	EU institutions /National Authorities/Regional Authorities/Local authorities
Standardisation bodies	EU Institutions
Research / Academia	Research Communities
Specialist Media	Research Communities

Comments on the target groups:

There are some challenges involved when addressing the project's target audience:

- ❖ The project is addressed to many different target groups, with significantly unique characteristics and needs, requiring different treatment. They come from distinct categories, socio/economic and educational groups, they have different points of view, agendas, and interests.
- ❖ The project is addressed to multiple countries with differing conditions, PED maturity levels, cultures, and communication codes.

The below figure demonstrates the broad variation between the project's target groups, in terms of expertise. These challenges require the plan to be flexible, to adapt to all these different needs, to combine them and offer solutions that cover them at the same time in the best possible way.

Figure 3: Relationship between target groups' expertise and type of body

5 KEY MESSAGES & MAIN COMMUNICATION ELEMENTS

5.1 Key Messages

The key messages for the project's communication towards the project's target groups are the following:

Main message:

- ❖ PEDvolution paves the way for cross-sectoral integration of ever-evolving PEDs.

Secondary messages:

- ❖ PEDvolution accommodates the constant evolution of PEDs.
- ❖ PEDvolution solutions will design, optimise, and strengthen the PEDs genotype and phenotype.
- ❖ PEDvolution addresses key challenges in PED development and evolution.
- ❖ PEDvolution brings solutions to enable PEDs to evolve and adapt in a changing and challenging environment.
- ❖ PEDvolution paves the way for replication, upscaling and mainstreaming of the developed PED solutions.
- ❖ PEDvolution brings together all involved actors in PED development.
- ❖ PEDvolution supports Europe to gain power in the global energy competition, while preserving its values and social-economic way of life.

The above messages will be used when developing the project's C&D&E material, but also when addressing different target audiences during communication and dissemination activities. These messages are indicative and aim to give general direction to the C&D&E efforts. Additionally, they will be adapted and/or updated as required in terms of the language use and message when different target groups.

5.2 Communication Elements

5.2.1 Project Name

The project's name is of particular significance since it combines the acronym PED for "Positive Energy District" and the word "evolution". Thus, highlighting the strong analogy with the theory of evolution, given that PEDs are constantly developing due to ever-evolving changes in their environment such as social context, legislation, energy market, and increased electric vehicles. It implies that although the DNA between PEDs varies, the implementation and evolution of different PEDs is not a process of chance, but the environment determines the probability of success in the urban transition.

5.2.2 Project keywords and catchphrases

Keywords that characterise the project in an effective way include the following:

- ❖ Circular economy
- ❖ Citizens
- ❖ Decarbonisation
- ❖ Digital solutions and tools
- ❖ Energy efficiency
- ❖ Energy prosumers
- ❖ Evolution
- ❖ Energy market
- ❖ Energy manager
- ❖ Excess heat source
- ❖ Genotype
- ❖ Green buildings
- ❖ Green energy
- ❖ (Geo)politics
- ❖ ICT
- ❖ Industry
- ❖ Interoperability
- ❖ Local renewables
- ❖ Mobility
- ❖ Phenotype
- ❖ Positive Energy Districts
- ❖ Renewables
- ❖ Self-sufficiency
- ❖ Social innovation
- ❖ Sustainability
- ❖ Transition
- ❖ Urban development

D10.1. Plan for Exploitation and Dissemination

Catchphrases that characterise the project in an effective way include the following:

- ❖ Energy-flexible urban areas
- ❖ Energy management of buildings
- ❖ Business model Innovation
- ❖ Net zero greenhouse gas emissions
- ❖ PED Readiness Assessment
- ❖ Surplus production of renewable energy
- ❖ Paving the way for cross-sectoral integration of ever-evolving PEDs
- ❖ Accommodating the constant evolution of PEDs
- ❖ Interoperable solutions to streamline PED evolution and cross-sectoral integration
- ❖ Contributing to the development and constant evolution of PEDs

The above words and phrases will be used to create the project's communication material and documentation, either as a whole or as concepts or directions.

5.2.3 Content directions and wording

PEDvolution's written and verbal communication will follow the principles that are described below:

- ❖ Clear, and friendly wording, easy to read and understand.
- ❖ The use of materials produced specifically for experts (professionals, scientists, researchers, academics etc.) should be exclusively limited to this target group. They can be more technical and scientific and have a different format than the ones used for the wide public and non-expert individuals.
- ❖ In the materials addressed to non-experts, no advanced technical terms and wording should be used. If technical terms are essential, they will be accompanied by appropriate indexes and explanations so that everything is easily understood.
- ❖ Focus on key points, according to the target group each material is addressed to.

Indicatively:

- When addressing energy prosumers, focus on energy and financial savings and benefits from establishing a positive energy district in terms of environmental building value, increase in the quality of living, financial and personal benefits.
- When addressing energy service providers and professionals, focus on long-term financial, technical, and environmental benefits, including project details and procedures, and technical or scientific information.
- ❖ Communication materials and texts should be suitable for/compatible with as many target groups as possible, thus avoiding too many versions, but simultaneously not "sacrificing" the compatibility of each material with the target audience it is addressed to.
- ❖ Materials produced especially for the mass media should be compatible with as many sub-audiences as possible and easy to understand and suitable for non-experts, even if this means sacrificing a part of the scientific or technical information.

Table 9: Basic content directions for Non-Experts and Expert Groups

	NON-EXPERTS	EXPERTS
KNOWLEDGE ON TECHNICAL, SCIENTIFIC, BUSINESS SUBJECTS	Limited.	High (on their domain).
KIND OF INTEREST	Personal	Professional, scientific
EXPECTED PRIORITIES	<p>Personal benefits:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Financial savings - Easy, simple, safe, reliable - House value increase - Quality of living <p>+ Environment benefits (for many, but not all of them).</p>	<p>Professionals:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Commercial benefits - Easy, simple, safe, reliable - Accepted by client <p>Scientists:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Scientific value - Sufficient, reliable data <p>NGOs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Energy savings - Environment benefits <p>Authorities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Depending on domain
LANGUAGE TO BE USED	Simple, accessible, friendly, easy to understand.	More precise, clear, detailed, scientific
TECHNICAL / SCIENTIFIC TERMS	Limited use, only when necessary and always fairly explained and supported by indexes	More extended use, also depending on the expert’s domain.
TECHNICAL / SCIENTIFIC DATA AND INFORMATION	Limited use, only when necessary and always fairly explained, preferably through examples, images, graphs, and infographics.	Extended use, with fair documentation, supportive data and details, scientific validity.
USE OF TEXT / IMAGES	Limited length of text, concise, only providing the essential information. More extended use of images, graphs, examples, infographics.	More extended length of text, providing all technical / scientific information and supportive data required. Plus, supportive graphs, images, infographics.
REFERENCES	Always provided, directing to the project website and the social media accounts.	Always provided, directing to the project website and the social media accounts. Plus, possibly, physical hubs that can provide more information for experts.

5.2.4 Project vision & identity

The project identity is of vital importance, since it establishes a common conception both internally within the project consortium, and externally with regards to dissemination to stakeholders and target groups.

Project partners come from a wide range of fields, with different objectives and contexts. For this purpose, internally, partners have discussed and are working towards a common definition of a PED for the scope of this project, to ensure that a common vision throughout the project implementation and execution. Externally, the project's visual identity is essential to ensure a clear and solid message when communicating and disseminating the project to the target groups and the wider community. For this purpose, the visual identity has been developed and is presented analytically in [Chapter 6](#). Elements will be updated and modified as required, during project implementation.

5.2.5 Project spokespersons

PEDvolution spokespersons are individuals from any partner countries, who will be required to represent and disseminate the project at an event, to an external audience. SXS and INLE as the C&D&E Manager and Project Coordinator (PC) respectively, but also the Work Package Leaders (WPLs) and PED Managers can be considered to have a heavier responsibility in this sense, and to contribute more significantly towards this goal.

6 COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION TOOLS & CHANNELS

6.1 Project Visual Identity and Templates

[Task Leader: SXS]

Project communication material must be easily identified with the assistance of unified style and aesthetics. The following elements have been adopted within the frame of the project's corporate identity.

6.1.1 Project Logo, colours and basic aesthetics

During the project identity design, several alternative logos and variations were designed, taking into consideration the characteristics, the targets, the key messages, and the target audiences of the project.

The selected one (see [Figure 4](#) below), resembles a group of buildings of different structures within a city or neighbourhood connected in a circuit.

On the left end the cell symbol is depicted, while on the right side the earth ground symbol is represented, portraying the dependency on natural resources for energy production and consumption. The presentation of the buildings as a single entity, conveys the interdependent, self-sufficient nature of the PED. The predominant colour of the line is orange, symbolising energy, enthusiasm, and positivity. A deep blue is the colour of the title representing reliability and stability.

The tagline can be placed under the logo or not, depending on the use and size. In some cases, the full name of the project may have to be adapted under or beside the logo.

Figure 4: PEDvolution logo with and without tagline

6.1.2 Funding Authorities' logos and disclaimers

EU Co-funding notice and disclaimer

As stated in Article 17 of the GA, communication activities of the beneficiaries related to the action (including media relations, conferences, seminars, information material, such as brochures, leaflets, posters, presentations, etc., in electronic form, via traditional or social media, etc.), dissemination activities and any infrastructure, equipment, vehicles, supplies or major result funded by the grant must acknowledge the EU support and display the European flag (emblem).

Since the project is co-funded, the below logo should be displayed. The emblem will remain distinct and separate and cannot be modified by adding other visual marks, brands or text.

Figure 5: EU Co-funding notice

Additionally, the following disclaimer (translated into local languages, where appropriate), will be included in all the respective material.

"Co-funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or CINEA. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them."

SERI funding notice and reference

The SWISS partners have received funding from the State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SERI). Beneficiaries undertake the obligation to mention the funding of all written publications, reports and scientific publications as well as all public documents associated with the results of the project in line with the guidelines provided by SERI. For this purpose, the below references and logo are to be included in all project materials and outputs.

"The Swiss project participants received funding from the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SERI)"

Figure 6: SERI logo

Acknowledgement for Scientific Publications

The EU and SERI funding acknowledgement should also be included in all scientific publications developed within the scope of the project. For this purpose, a statement such as the one below, should be included in all relevant publications. The below acknowledgement is indicative and can be modified as required.

"Acknowledgement

This study/report/other was supported in part by the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement N° 101138472 (PEDvolution) and from the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SERI)."

6.1.3 Font sets, Text formation

Font family used in PEDvolution documentation:

- **Roboto** fonts
by **Google**

About Roboto

The new typeface, Roboto, was designed entirely in-house by Christian Robertson who previously had released an expanded Ubuntu Titling font through his personal type foundry Betatype. The font was officially made available for free download on January 12, 2012, on the newly launched Android Design website.

Compared to the humanist sans-serif Droid Sans, Roboto belongs to the neo-grotesque genre of sans-serif typefaces. It includes Thin, Light, Regular, Medium, Bold and Black weights with matching oblique styles rather than true italics. It also includes condensed styles in Light, Regular and Bold, also with matching oblique designs.

Link for more information and download: [Roboto](#)

License

These fonts are licensed under the [Apache License, Version 2.0](#).

It allows users to use the software for any purpose, to distribute it, to modify it, and to distribute modified versions of the software under the terms of the license, without concern for royalties.

You can use them freely in your products & projects - print or digital, commercial or otherwise. However, you can't sell the fonts on their own.

This isn't legal advice, please consider consulting a lawyer and see the full license for all details.

6.1.4 Presentation template

A basic presentation template in .pptx format is provided, including a variety of slide formats.

D10.1. Plan for Exploitation and Dissemination

(See [ANNEX I](#)).

6.1.5 Report/Deliverable template

A report/deliverable template in .docx format is provided, for use when developing official project deliverables.

(See [ANNEX I](#)).

6.1.6 Meeting agenda and Minutes template

A Meeting agenda and Minutes template is provided in .docx format.

(See [ANNEX I](#)).

6.1.7 Web Design elements

The project's website is already on air, at <https://pedvolution.eu/>

More content will be added on a regular basis, as it is made available.

(See also [ANNEX I](#)).

6.1.8 News Alerts template

A News Alert template is provided in .pptx format.

(See [ANNEX I](#)).

6.1.9 Social media identity headers & avatars

Social media identity, headers, covers, and avatars are provided for social media pages.

(See [ANNEX I](#)).

6.2 Communication Tools: Printable Materials

A variety of printable communication tools will be used throughout the project lifetime. Their role is to present PEDvolution, its objectives, key messages, operation, and outcomes in an effective and comprehensible manner.

Specifically:

[Task Leader: SXS]

The printable communication tools will be developed for use during the project's lifetime.

They will be available in electronic format but created with specifications that allow them to be printed if/when needed. They may be printed centrally (e.g. for use/distribution in physical events and presentations), or by users after downloading them through the project website).

6.2.1 Brochure

The brochure is addressed to a wide public, mainly to non-experts, prosumers, and citizens. Nevertheless, it may also serve professionals and experts, providing awareness and information about PEDvolution.

Its purpose is to raise awareness and attract attention about the project, providing basic information, and redirect interested parties to more detailed sources for further information. It contains a basic description and information about the project, its concept and objectives, and basic instructions for participating. It will also provide sources for more information: the website address, social networks accounts, etc. It can be used on screen, or printed as a trifold with page size of 20x20 cm.

It is firstly developed in English and adapted to all 6 project languages i.e. Greek, French, Dutch, Slovenian, German and Norwegian. (See [ANNEX II](#)).

6.2.2 Poster

The poster is also addressed to a wide public, and mainly to non-experts, prosumers, and citizens. Nevertheless, it may also serve professionals and experts, providing awareness and information about PEDvolution and its goals.

Its purpose is to raise awareness and attract attention about the project, providing basic information, and redirect interested parties to more detailed sources for further information. It contains a basic description and information about the project, its concept and objectives, and basic instructions for participating. It will also provide sources for more information: the website address, social networks accounts, etc. It can be used on screen or printed.

It is firstly developed in English and adapted to all 6 project languages i.e. Greek, French, Dutch, Slovenian, German and Norwegian. (See [ANNEX II](#)).

6.2.3 Roll-up Banner

The roll-up banner (with dimensions 85x200 cm) is mainly intended for use in events, presentations, conferences, congresses, etc.

It is addressed to the events' participants, which may be experts (e.g. energy providers, PED developers) or non-experts, depending on the event's nature, aiming to raise awareness and attract attention about the project and provide basic information on its objectives, aims and results. It also provides sources for more information on the project such as the website address and social networks accounts. (See [ANNEX II](#)).

6.3 Online communication Channels and Resources

6.3.1 Social media posts

[Task Leader: SXS]

Posts on social networks (i.e. LinkedIn, Twitter, and YouTube), will be used to disseminate project's results and engage with stakeholders. These posts may contain information and updates about the progress and outcomes of the project, news, reports, infographics, announcements, and sharing of information published on the project website.

However, social networks may be powerful, though not risk-free. All sorts of posts and publications will be carefully and clearly expressed and formatted, minimising the possibility of being misinterpreted.

Even more caution is required when it comes to the management of comments, questions, objections or even "attacks" by users. Any possible online dialogue with the public will be performed with caution. In case of online attack, opposition, or conflict it is important to handle the situation in a way depleting tension and avoiding further complications.

The source of the information used in the posts can only be the project partners. SXS is the administrator of the social network accounts and publishes the materials provided by the project partners. The regular feed of the social networks is important for the engagement with the stakeholders and the effective promotion of the project.

Project partners will also be asked to use their own accounts to share these communication elements, so to obtain wider coverage.

Figure 7: PEDvolution LinkedIn and Twitter accounts

6.3.2 Project Website

[Task Leader: SXS]

The project website is developed as the information hub for PEDvolution and its outputs, as well as for potential follow-up exploitation initiative(s). It is a critical channel for the communication, dissemination, and exploitation of project information and results. It will contain all the information any stakeholder/interested party could possibly search out, or at least links to the locations where this information can be found in case it is not stored directly on the website.

It is set up on a modern Content Management System (CMS) infrastructure, allowing quick updates, integration of external material, a high degree of interactivity, and rapid search/access to the content by users.

From its outset, the website will provide information on the project's background, objectives, progress, news, events, and public outputs. Visitors will be able to subscribe to news alerts, follow updates by RSS, and access/download public material.

The website will include advanced functions such as video content streaming via embedded YouTube and Twitter feeds, cross-referenced navigation, secure login, malware protection supported by professional services.

The website content will be in English, as the project's official working language. It will be designed, developed and kept updated by SXS. Updates will be regular, at least once per month and whenever new public outputs are made available. All partners will contribute to the provision of relevant information and material, throughout the project's lifetime.

Link to the website: <https://pedvolution.eu/>.

6.3.3 News Alerts

[Task Leader: SXS]

News Alerts are short announcements containing information and brief updates about the progress and outcomes of the project. Their primary purpose is to attract the interest of the project's target groups and persuade them to find out more about the project. News alerts may contain information such as news, reports, infographics, announcements, and sharing of information published on the project's website.

They will be sent to the project's contact list at least bi-annually and redistributed through the project website as well as partners' websites, social media pages, and newsletters.

The information included in the News Alerts, will only be provided by the project partners, sharing the progress, outcomes, news, and announcements of their Work Packages with SXS. It is important for each partner to share information from their side regarding project progress, so News Alerts can depict a complete picture of the project's overall progress.

6.3.4 GDPR-compliant contacts database

[Task Leader: SXS]

In order to streamline contact management for the project, while supporting the various activities requiring networking under their specific WPs, a common contacts database will be set up by month 12 (December 2024), which will include interested parties, stakeholders, media contacts etc.

Access will be provided to the relevant Task Leaders (TLs) under GDPR compliant terms. This database will be used to share all project outputs through the News Alerts, to gather participants to PEDvolution events and more.

It will integrate relevant contacts provided via the project partners, through a registration form on the website, and through PEDvolution event participants.

To allow recipients to unsubscribe at any time, a clearly identifiable link will also be put in News Alerts and other automated mailings.

6.3.5 Advertorial Video

[Task Leader: SXS]

A short (3'-5') advertorial video will be produced by month 24 (December 2025), presenting the project in English, with subtitled versions for all project languages, explaining in an easy-to-understand way PEDvolution's ambitions and preliminary results in the context of the EU's climate and energy goals. The video will be based on brief statements by representatives of the project partners during a planned meeting.

It will be made available as streaming video via YouTube, as well as in a high-resolution version for free broadcast (provided on demand).

Links to it will also be placed on the website, posts in social networks, News Alerts, as well as material distributed to the media.

6.3.6 Digital presentation

[Task Leader: SXS]

The project's digital presentation available in .pptx format has been developed in month 5 (May 2024), and contains an overview of the scope, objectives, and aspirations. The slides include basic information on the project, so that it can be used as a basis, modified, and enriched with additional information as required. The primary purpose is for the presentation to be used when presenting the project to a wider or targeted audience during 3rd party events and relevant opportunities.

(See [ANNEX III](#)).

6.3.7 Digital Gateways –Data Hubs

[Task Leader: SXS]

Public deliverables and announcements of the project will be submitted to relevant data hubs such as BUILD UP and Construction 21, shortly after posting them at the project website.

This is a critical channel both for communication and dissemination of the project's information and results. It is primarily addressed to specific -important- categories of stakeholders that use these gateways (i.e. ESCOs, PED developers and managers, Investors, local/regional authorities and policy makers).

BUILD UP

The European Portal For Energy Efficiency In Buildings

6.4 Communication Matrix

The following matrix describes the connections between target groups, communication tools and channels. Capital bold “X” shows a significant connection, while lower case normal weight “x” shows a secondary one.

Table 10: Relationship between Target groups and Communication Tools and Channels

Target Groups / Sub-Groups	Tools					Channels & Resources							
	Brochure	Poster	Roll-up Banner	News Alerts	Social Media Posts	Media Coverage	Advertorial Video	Website	GDPR contacts	Social Networks	Digital Gateways	3rd party Events	Final EU Conference
DEMAND SIDE													
Residents/ Energy consumers /End users	X	X			X	X	X	X		X			
Energy prosumers	X	X			X	X	X	X		X			
SUPPLY SIDE													
Energy service providers, (ESCOs) & Mobility service providers	X	X	X		X	X	X	X		X			
Energy prosumers	X	X	X		X	X	X	X		X			
PED developers and managers	x	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Local authorities and city planners	x	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
PUBLIC SIDE													
Policy makers				X	x	X	X	X	X	x	X	x	x
Energy prosumers	x	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Standardisation bodies	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	x	X	X
Research / Academia connected to energy efficiency in buildings	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	x	X	X
University departments connected to energy efficiency and construction	x	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
EU public authorities	x	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
National public authorities	x	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Regional/local public authorities, municipalities	x	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Specialist Media with a focus on energy efficiency of buildings and construction	x	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
General public	X	X			X	X	X	X		X			
FINANCIAL SIDE													
PED Investors (banks, real estate developers, regional funders)	x	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	x	X	X

7 EXPERT COMMUNICATION & DISSEMINATION ACTIVITIES & NETWORKS

7.1 3rd Party Events

[Task Leader: SXS]

3rd party events are thematically relevant events organised by external partners to the PEDvolution consortium (whether they are events organised by thematically relevant EU projects, relevant initiatives, or thematically targeted events).

It is expected that PEDvolution partners will participate in at least 3 relevant EU-level events, where it will be possible to efficiently reach the project target groups, disseminate project results and identify opportunities for their further exploitation. Specifically, the project will be represented in at least 2 EU-level events during the 2nd year of implementation (i.e. January - December 2025) and in at least 1 EU-level event during the 3rd year of implementation (i.e. January - December 2026).

In addition, PEDvolution partners will attend at least 5 relevant national and/or regional events, throughout the project duration. PEDvolution will be represented in at least 2 respective events during the 2nd year of implementation and at least 3 during the 3rd year of implementation.

[Table 11](#) below, presents several indicative EU/International 3rd party events primarily planned for the 1st year of the project, in which PEDvolution partners can promote and disseminate early project results, while contributing to maximising overall project impact. [Table 12](#) on the other hand, presents several national/regional relevant 3rd party events that respective project partners can attend.

Table 11: Indicative EU/International 3rd Party Events

NO.	EVENT	DATE(S)	CITY/AREA	COUNTRY	LINK
1	European Environmental Bureau 50 th Anniversary Conference	13/05/2024	Brussels	Belgium	https://eeb.org/eeb-50th-anniversary-conference-2024-13-may-2024-brussels/
2	BuildSIM Nordic	09-11/06/2024	Espoo	Finland	https://buildsimnordic2024.ibpsa-nordic.org/
3	European Sustainable Energy Week	11-13/06/2024	Brussels	Belgium	https://sustainable-energy-week.ec.europa.eu/index_en
4	Intersolar	19-21/06/2024	Munich	Germany	https://www.intersolar.de/start
5	International Conference on Energy Efficiency in Buildings	20-21/06/2024	Vienna	Austria	https://waset.org/energy-efficiency-in-buildings-conference-in-june-2024-in-vienna?utm_source=conferenceindex&utm_medium=referral&utm_campaign=listing
6	6 th Building Simulation Applications Conference	26-28/06/2024	Bozen-Bolzano (South Tyrol)	Italy	https://bsa.events.unibz.it/
7	Lisbon Energy Summit and Exhibition	27-29/06/2024	Lisbon	Portugal	https://www.lisbonenergysummit.com/visit/visitor-registration/?utm_source=google-search&utm_medium=cpc&utm_term=energy%20exhibition&utm_content=&utm_campaign=visprom
8	Global Energy Transition Congress and Exhibition	01-03/07/2024	Milan	Italy	https://www.getcongress.com/
9	Sustainable Places (hybrid)	23-25/09/2024	Luxembourg	Luxembourg	https://www.sustainableplaces.eu/
10	17 th International Conference on Energy and Climate Change	09-11/10/2024	Athens	Greece	promitheasconference.wordpress.com
11	ENLIT Europe	22-24/10/2024	Milan	Italy	https://www.enlit-europe.com/about
12	Future of utilities Energy transition summit	19-20/03/2025	Amsterdam	Netherlands	https://futureofutilities.com/events/energy-transition-summit/

D10.1. Plan for Exploitation and Dissemination

Table 12: Indicative National/Regional 3rd Party Events

NO.	EVENT	DATE	CITY/AREA	COUNTRY	LINK
1	Energy Efficiency in Buildings conference	05/04/2024	Athens	Greece	https://www.energyefficiencyinbuildings.gr/agenda-energy-efficiency-in-buildings-conference/
2	Sustainability Summit Austria	06-07/06/2024	Graz	Austria	https://www.fifteenseconds.com/festival/graz-2024/sustainable-europe?source=googleads&gad_source=1&gclid=Cj0KCQjwztOwBhD7ARIsAPDKnkBBZD-2nLtmZmE47Q6m_OaprEPKR8fS9i8SXEzIbyJn5FZU8oM2MCYaAvfuEALw_wcB
3	Net-Zero Future 2024	19-21/06/2024	Oslo	Norway	https://netzfuture.com/conference/
4	InnoRenew CoE 2024	11-12/09/2024	Izola	Slovenia	https://innorenew.eu/innorenew-coe-international-conference-2024/
5	Energy Future	05/11/2024	Aarau	Switzerland	https://www.electrosuisse.ch/fr/manifestations/energiezukunft/
6	Swiss Electricity Congress	15-16/01/2025	Bern	Switzerland	https://www.stromkongress.ch/fr

7.2 Final Conference at EU-level

[Task Leader: SXS]

A final conference will be organised in Brussels, primarily aiming to raise awareness and disseminate the PEDvolution project outcomes and results at the EU-level, thereby significantly contributing to maximising project's impact.

The conference will be organised at the end of the project (between month 34 – month 36), coinciding with the last project meeting. Project partners and external experts will contribute as speakers or to panel discussions. The goal is to gather more than 120 participants, with a possible link to other relevant events, such as the European Sustainable Energy Week (EUSEW) or the European Week of Regions and Cities (EWRC), thereby encouraging the development of potential policy recommendations.

All project partners will be involved in the agenda and participate with physical presence during the event. The event will be summarised in a text briefing on the website; presentations will be recorded and shared via the project's YouTube channel.

7.3 The BRIDGE Initiative

7.3.1 Purpose and requirements

[Task Leader: INLE]

The PEDvolution collaboration plan involves a series of activities to establish contacts with relevant European projects, especially with sister projects funded under the topic HORIZON-CL5-2023-D4-01-03 - Interoperable solutions for PEDs, including a better integration of local renewables and local excess heat sources, such as [InterPED](#) (Grant Number 101138047) and HARMONISE (Grant Number 101138595), as well as with the BRIDGE initiative and other wider networks, associations and initiatives on Energy Efficiency, Renewables, Smart Grids, Storage and similar topics addressed within the frame of PEDvolution. The objective is to capitalise on the created network in order to organise joint events and activities with the different research and innovation actions. Coordination and communication efforts enable PEDvolution to share experiences and knowledge in the relevant Research & Development (R&D) fields.

BRIDGE is a European Commission initiative which unites Horizon 2020 and Horizon Europe Smart Grid, Energy Storage, Islands, and Digitalisation Projects, involving 155 projects in total (among which 97 are ongoing and 58 ended as of 1st of July 2023) tallying 1510 organisations from 39 countries, to create a structured view of cross-cutting issues which are encountered in the demonstration projects and may constitute an obstacle to innovation. The BRIDGE process fosters continuous knowledge sharing amongst projects thus allowing them to deliver conclusions and recommendations about the future exploitation of the project results, with a single voice, through four different Working Groups representing the main areas of interest: a) Data Management, b) Business models, c) Regulation and d) Consumer and Citizen Engagement.

Effective communication and collaboration will facilitate knowledge exchange and incorporation of lessons learned from ongoing demonstration projects. Tapping into the experiences of other initiatives and the aggregated know-how, PEDvolution can overcome barriers to effective innovation and ensure the successful implementation of its own solutions. Furthermore, participation in BRIDGE and similar initiatives aligns with PEDvolution's objectives of promoting interoperability and standardisation within the smart grid domain. The project will embrace best practices in data management, regulation, consumer engagement, and business model development, as identified by the various Working Groups (WGs) within BRIDGE.

To fulfil these objectives, PEDvolution partners are required to actively engage with the BRIDGE initiative and other relevant consortia. The involvement includes attending meetings, contributing to working group activities, and sharing project insights and outcomes. Additionally, partners must establish communication channels with other EU projects, standardisation organisations, and national/international bodies to foster collaboration and exchange knowledge.

Moreover, during the 1st year of the project, PEDvolution has made significant strides in its engagement efforts, including contacting the BRIDGE initiative, establishing registered contact points per BRIDGE and assigning partners to the related WGs providing a Project Description template for the 2024 Brochure, delivering a demo site fact sheet that will be included in the BRIDGE Use Case Repository. In addition, PEDvolution has attracted attention from external networks such as the [Scalable Cities](#) initiative, [ETIP-SNET](#), ISGAN and the [Smart Cities Marketplace](#).

D10.1. Plan for Exploitation and Dissemination

A layout of the liaison and synergies plan is shown in [Figure 8](#), identifying 4 phases, described below:

Phase 1: Initial Engagement and Networking (Year 1 – T10.2)

- Identify and establish contact with key projects, consortia, and initiatives including BRIDGE, AIOTI, Annex 83, COST Action on PEDs, interoperability and standardisation initiatives, and national/international bodies like InterConnect and FlexCommunity.eu.
- Participate in relevant events and assemblies such as the annual general assembly of BRIDGE to network and identify potential synergies.
- Specify activities and areas of interest for collaboration with the BRIDGE initiative and other partners.
- Share project goals and gather inputs from ongoing initiatives to inform the co-design of PED-RA and other PEDvolution solutions.

Phase 2: Capacity Building and Knowledge Sharing (Year 1-2 – T10.2 & T11.3)

- Continue liaison activities to foster collaboration and knowledge exchange.
- Facilitate capacity building activities for PED co-developers and demonstrators, leveraging experiences shared through initiatives like the "PED demonstrators call."
- Engage with ambassadors of PEDs to gather insights and share best practices.
- Contribute to BRIDGE general assembly, Working Groups, and annual work programs, actively exchanging experiences and insights with other projects.

Phase 3: Collaboration and Contribution (Year 2-3 – T11.3 & T12.2)

- Deepen collaboration with BRIDGE and other EU initiatives, actively contributing to their activities and projects.
- Present testing and validation results of the PED-Readiness Assessment to BRIDGE and other relevant EU-initiatives.
- Provide evidence and insights from project experiences to inform policy actions and discussions.
- Explore opportunities for standardisation and replication of project results across Europe through discussions with BRIDGE and other stakeholders.

Phase 4: Sustainability and Legacy (Year 3 – T12.2)

- Evaluate the impact and effectiveness of collaboration efforts with BRIDGE and other initiatives.
- Document lessons learned, best practices, and outcomes of collaboration activities.
- Develop strategies for sustaining and expanding collaboration beyond the project duration.
- Advocate for the adoption of project results and standards within relevant policy frameworks and initiatives.

D10.1. Plan for Exploitation and Dissemination

Figure 8: Phases of the PEDvolution liaison and synergies plan

In the contemporary energy landscape, a just and green energy transition is pivotal, spurred by the pressing need to combat climate change and turn towards sustainable energy paradigms. Central to this transformative journey are endeavours aimed at developing PEDs, energy entities designed to generate surplus energy, thereby strengthening local energy grids. These initiatives centre around collaborative frameworks, necessitating robust knowledge dissemination, interdisciplinary exchanges, and adept networking among stakeholders ranging from policymakers to grassroots communities. In PEDvolution a liaison plan under development in T10.2 and reported in D10.2, aims to enhance networking and outreach impact within the project ambition.

In addition, the liaison plan serves as a channel for the dissemination of pertinent knowledge and insights connected to the energy transition landscape. To this end a set of targeted outreach endeavours, such as workshops, symposia, and colloquia, participants in the liaison task will spotlight best practices, nascent technologies, and policy strengths and weaknesses. Targeting stakeholders through a consortium with a multidisciplinary composition, the liaison plan not only facilitates the seamless transfer of knowledge but also expedites the uptake of transformative solutions.

In a cyclical fashion, the liaison plan can pinpoint effective avenues for dissemination and knowledge exchange, strengthening the transferability of PEDvolution results meantime materialising an iterative process of introspection and adaptation, fortifying stakeholders against the hindrances of emergent challenges and evolving paradigms. As PEDvolution prioritises the enhancement of interoperability between assets, stakeholders, and systems, the work under T10.2 will contribute to nurturing an ecosystem where innovation converges with co-development.

7.3.2 Partners' roles and expected participation

Within the BRIDGE initiative, PEDvolution partners are assigned specific roles and responsibilities based on their expertise and areas of interest. For example, partners may participate in working groups focusing on data management, consumer and citizen engagement, or business model innovation. In these groups, partners are expected to contribute their knowledge, insights, and experiences to collaborative efforts according to the BRIDGE WG action plans.

Partners' participation in BRIDGE extends beyond mere attendance at meetings or events. They are actively involved in discussions, workshops, and knowledge-sharing activities, ensuring that PEDvolution's interests and objectives are effectively represented. Additionally, partners play a key role in identifying synergies between PEDvolution and other initiatives, exploring opportunities for collaboration, and sharing relevant project deliverables and outcomes. More specifically, during the first year of the project, PEDvolution has actively engaged in the annual general assembly of BRIDGE, where it has identified potential synergies with various BRIDGE WGs. Specifically, PEDvolution has contributed to the following BRIDGE WGs:

- Data Management WG, with ICOM serving as a member.
- Consumer and Citizen Engagement WG, led by SIN.
- Business Models WG, with SIN also participating as a member.

7.3.3 Other EU Initiatives

In addition to BRIDGE, PEDvolution partners are tasked with establishing connections with other EU initiatives and projects, such as Scalable Cities, [AIOTI](#), [Annex 83](#), and the [COST Action on PEDS](#). These engagements serve to broaden the project's network, facilitate knowledge exchange, and identify potential areas of collaboration or synergy. By participating in these initiatives, PEDvolution can leverage additional resources, expertise, and opportunities to enhance its impact and achieve its goals.

Partners' involvement in other EU initiatives involves active participation in meetings, workshops, and collaborative activities. They are responsible for representing PEDvolution's interests, sharing project insights, and exploring avenues for cooperation with other stakeholders. Through these engagements, partners contribute to the broader ecosystem of smart grid development and help position PEDvolution as a leading initiative in the field.

PEDvolution also capitalises on the involvement of project partners in ongoing EU projects activated in the district and buildings energy performance and efficiency domain such as [OPENLab](#) (VITO, SXS), [syn.ikia](#) (NTNU), [ARV](#) (NTNU), [PROBONO](#) (INLE, SIN), as well as energy management tools, optimisation, business tools and models, and markets PLATOON (OFFSET), [FEVER](#) (ESG, ICOM, SWW), [E-LAND](#) (SIN, ICOM) to on-board lessons learnt and knowledge generated within these projects but also engage in networking and liaison activities.

PEDvolution will be also actively liaising with EU projects on PEDs:

- a) For key learnings and findings with the [LC-SC3-SCC-1-2018-2019-2020 - Smart Cities and Communities](#) funded projects, leveraging their common involvement in EU Initiatives such as the **Scalable Cities Platform** and the **Smart Cities marketplace** (e.g., **POCITYF** GA ID: 864400, **ATELIER** GA ID: 864374)
- b) **HORIZON-MISS-2023-CIT-01-02** funded projects: **TIPS4PED** GA ID: 101139633, **EXPEDITE** GA ID: 101139527, **BIPED** GA ID: 101139060
- c) [LC-GD-4-1-2020 - Building and renovating in an energy and resource efficient way](#) projects

8 KEY EXPLOITATION RESULTS (KERS) & EXPLOITATION PATHWAYS

8.1 Key Exploitable Results

As defined in the Horizon Europe, program manual, a Key Exploitable Result (KER) is an identified main interesting result, which has been selected and prioritised due to its high potential to be “exploited” – meaning to make use and derive benefits- downstream the value chain of a product, process or solution, or act as an important input to policy, further research or education.

PEDvolution has identified 7 KERs presented in the following [Section 8.2](#), which are foreseen to be developed as interoperable solutions within the scope of the project. Still, it is important to note that throughout the project duration and specifically as foreseen in task T11.2 “KERs update and characterisation”, additional KERs may be identified.

8.2 Exploitation Pathways

KERs (as currently defined), their description and exploitation intention are presented in [Table 13](#).

Within the scope of tasks T11.2 “KERs update and characterisation” & T12.3 “Sustainability plan, exploitation and replications”, when project results have matured, all project will be analysed in depth. The list of KERs will be updated (if/as required) and reported in D11.2, with any additional KERs including their characterisation, to mitigate any possible related risks and make the necessary corrections in a timely manner.

In the final year of project implementation, starting from the updated list of KERs and their characterisation, the exploitation plan will be defined, by prioritising and doing need assessment based on KERs exploitation potential, the exploitation intention by the solutions and service providers, considering the IPR strategy defined. This will lead to the development of deliverable D12.2 “PEDvolution replication and market analysis & exploitation strategy”, which will map specific individual and joint exploitation strategies for each KER for the most promising KPIs.

Table 13: PEDvolution KERs and exploitation pathways

KER TITLE	KER DESCRIPTION	KER OWNER/S	EXPLOITATION	POTENTIAL TARGET GROUPS	SUGGESTED IPR PROTECTION STRATEGY
PEDvolution GENOTYPE SOLUTIONS					
PED Design and Planning Toolset	A Digital Twin planning tool to empower developers and managers to accelerate district development pathways towards achieving or further evolving a PED. The tool will provide accurate energy models of buildings and district assets as a basis to generate renovation pathways along district heating/cooling grids based on local conditions. A robust and future-proof solution is provided by the tool, enabling evidence-based and informed decision-making to reduce risks caused by techno-economic uncertainties.	VITO TUW	Commercial exploitation, research and publication	TG1 TG4 TG5 TG9	To be completed once project results have matured.
Dynamic Decision Support Guideline	Targeted guidelines and efficient workflow for PED development decisions related to the choice of technologies and strategies with respect to urban planning, energy efficiency and integration of local renewables.	NTNU VITO	Commercial exploitation and further research	TG1 TG4 TG5 TG6 TG7 TG9	Same as above.
PEDvolution PHENOTYPE SOLUTIONS					

D10.1. Plan for Exploitation and Dissemination

KER TITLE	KER DESCRIPTION	KER OWNER/S	EXPLOITATION	POTENTIAL TARGET GROUPS	SUGGESTED IPR PROTECTION STRATEGY
PED Energy Manager	Multi-level toolset for efficient management of energy processes within PED. The Energy Manager controls energy processes in residential and non-residential environments, assesses and extracts flexibility, optimises the operation in multi-sector environment and exploits flexibility on several energy and flexibility markets.	OFFSET (formerly RENN) TUW ICOM	Commercial exploitation	TG1 TG3 TG4 TG6 TG9	Same as above.
Data Exchange, Integration & Interoperability Platform	Mechanisms for secure data exchanges within the boundaries of the PED ecosystem, as well as with the external environment, facilitating access to the data through standard interfaces, whilst making sure that proper privacy policies apply.	ICOM OFFSET (formerly RENN)	Commercial exploitation and further research	TG1 TG5 TG7 TG9	Same as above.
PED Readiness Assessment	This assessment methodology is a systematic process of monitoring and determining the performance of a neighbourhood or district, in relation to the essential characteristics of a Positive Energy District. This will build further on different frameworks from other European and international initiatives. All criteria will be structured with a focus on clarity, readability and user-friendliness. The structure is designed in such a way that the aspects most relevant to project decision-makers are placed first. A life cycle perspective is given on how the system will further address the respective criterion in the future.	ZHAW VITO SIN NTNU	Commercial exploitation, further research, open results, publication and policy exploitation	TG1 TG4 TG5 TG7 TG8 TG9	Same as above.
PED Business Models Innovation Tool	This business model innovation tool will provide a set of building blocks, known as 'business model patterns,' that have been proven successful in community-based business solutions. The tool's process will show PEDs how to adapt	SIN	Further research and publication	TG1 TG4 TG6 TG9	Same as above.

D10.1. Plan for Exploitation and Dissemination

KER TITLE	KER DESCRIPTION	KER OWNER/S	EXPLOITATION	POTENTIAL TARGET GROUPS	SUGGESTED IPR PROTECTION STRATEGY
	business model patterns to the local context and combine them to create promising business models.				
PED Social Innovation Tool	This social innovation and engagement tool is a methodology that allows to assess the state of the community and to understand the priorities, values and views of different stakeholders or actors to design an energy solution or related activities to be compatible with local needs. The aim is to contribute to long lasting adoption of planned or existing energy innovation in a PED. The methodology is a 3-phased process consisting of information collection, analysis, and co-creation and engagement planning, with tools available for each step after which the PEDs should be able to implement the activities themselves.	SIN	Further research and publication	TG1 TG4 TG6 TG9	Same as above.

9 EXPLOITATION IN MARKET AND POLICY

9.1 Business Plan and Path to Commercialisation

Figure 9 describes core value creation, value proposition, and value capture aspects of the PEDvolution project based on the following Business Model Canvas (BMC). The approach used for developing the project level BMC will be adapted to each PEDs context during the implementation of the project. The integration of these aspects during the project and iterations at pilot PEDs will lead to significant benefits in terms of social, technology, interoperability, market, and independency aspects. The foreseen replication activities, which will also last beyond the project lifecycle, and lead to beyond EU-wide level to the significant impacts outlined at Figure 11 (Section 9.3).

VALUE CREATION		VALUE PROPOSITION			VALUE CAPTURE	
PLAYERS	ACTIVITIES	SOCIAL	TECHNOLOGY	MARKET	RELATIONSHIPS	USERS
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PED managers and users (Residents, Commercial and Industries) • TSOs/DSOs • Aggregators • Authorities • Technology service providers • ESCOs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PED engagement • Awareness raising/education • Energy sharing/ trading • Collective self-consumption • SW/HW provision for energy services • Flexibility aggregation and trading • Grid support services 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • New forms of human-centred cooperation of local actors • Increased local networking and sustainability awareness • Fighting energy poverty 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stable and secure power supply • Losses reduction • Automation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Market access to PEDs and end users • International best PED practice examples for regulatory bodies • PED cooperation with regulators • Peak shaving 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Customer support services • Surveys • Interviews • Digital apps 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PED managers • Individual consumers and households (B2B2C) • SMEs • Commercial entities • Industrial sites
RESOURCES		INTEROPERABILITY	INDEPENDENCY		CHANNELS	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Human resources • RES and other energy assets • Local energy data access • PEDvolution SW & HW • Integrated processes for the energy value chain 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Integrated, interoperable and standardised systems & protocols • Value stacking 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increased self-consumption • Reducing reliance on imports of energy sources • Replacement of energy sources through waste-energy recuperation 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Engagement activities • General public marketing campaigns • Site events • Scientific reports • Workshops 	
COSTS				BENEFITS		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Solution engineering – system integration services • Hardware and software solution provision and support services • Turn-key implementation • Input costs for energy / transformation costs (e.g. biomass) • Technical education, training • Energy consulting for identification of waste energy potential • Communal investments 				<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Savings from cross energy-vector optimisation • Innovative products with short lead-times • Flexibility market revenues • Recurring revenues from grid services • Leveraging future investments in R&I for PEDs and savings through participation in national/European financing programs 		

Figure 9: PEDvolution Business Model Canvas

9.2 Contribution to Standardisation, Policy, and Regulation

Given that project partners are largely involved in multiple EU and international initiatives, as well as with interoperability and pre-standardisation initiatives and national/international bodies, (mentioned in [Section 7.3](#)), early networking activities of PEDvolution, will play a crucial role in the development of the project's activities and will also serve to take advantage of other running initiatives' results, regarding exploitation and replication potential. The main partners to be involved in this process are INLE (AIOTI, Scalable Cities, ETIP-SNET), ZHAW (ANNEX 83, COST Action on PEDs), VITO (ANNEX 83), SIN (ANNEX 83), NTNU (ANNEX 83), ICOM (InterConnect, FlexCommunity.eu), OFFSET (FlexCommunity) as members of the respective initiatives.

Liaison with initiatives and lobbies will play an important role in the development of the PED Readiness Assessment methodology (developed within WP4) aimed to support PEDs on the energy transition, as well as the other PEDvolution solutions. Via this process valuable input will be collected. The below figure represents the steps to be taken at each stage of the project, as regards the involvement in the initiatives which will encourage the development and exploitation of project results.

Figure 10: Collaboration between PEDvolution partners and EU initiatives and lobbies

Furthermore, PEDvolution will support the provision of advice and evidence for EU policy making through its active involvement in several **BRIDGE** WGs. initiative Data Management Working Group. As mentioned in [Section 7.3.2](#) ICOM as member of the Data Management WG, SIN as a member of the BRIDGE Business Models and Consumer and Citizen engagement WG, will contribute towards this goal. Additionally, through different Groups of **AIOTI** (most relevant are the Energy Group and the Buildings Group) PEDvolution, and namely INLE who is AIOTI member, will contribute on a wider scale to the research agenda on energy, buildings, IoT vision and roadmap relating to energy efficiency in buildings,

D10.1. Plan for Exploitation and Dissemination

integration of local renewables and local excess heat sources within districts, and environmental/energy related policies.

Finally, in the second half of the project, PEDvolution will request project liaison with **CEN/TC 465 on Sustainable Cities and Communities** where it will contribute the project results and benefit from the results of the committee.

9.3 Follow-up plan after the project ends

After the end of the project, it is expected that partners will continue to implement several actions, especially the market uptake and the ongoing operation in PEDs (Figure 11). Indeed, a key approach of the PEDvolution solution is the sustainability of PEDs’ participation in the energy market. Therefore, both Solution Providers and PED Managers will ensure that the solutions deployed in the scope of the project are maintained and curated in the long term.

Business schemes will be co-developed in WP6 “PED Business and social innovation tools”, then refined and validated during the demonstration activities in WP9 “PEDvolution demonstrators and performance assessment” and funding research (private and public R&I funding) will be considered in T9.2 “PEDvolution tool refinement and technical support” to implement this path.

Depending on the use cases and associated business cases as well as KERs, the PEDvolution partners will decide on the different exploitation routes, including agreements for specific and general exploitation purposes to this aim, that will be discussed in the C&D&E – WP12 during Year 3 of project implementation. Additionally, a follow-up will be done on end users reached through communication and dissemination, together with liaison and replication activities.

Guided by SXS as C&D&E Manager, activity T12.3 “Sustainability plan, exploitation, and replication” will ensure that most promising areas across Europe are identified for replicating KERs. TUW as TL of Subtask 12.3.2 “Replication and market analysis” will identify key success criteria for making PEDvolution solutions work in PEDs, districts close to PEDs and other contexts. As a next step a dataset of the identified criteria across typologies of districts will be set-up and TUW will assess the possible evolution of these criteria in coming years and decades. As a final step, TUW will assess the potential to replicate the PEDvolution solutions under the variety of conditions and assess the impacts on KPIs such as GHG-emissions, energy demand or economic indicators.

This will facilitate the transition from the PEDvolution project phase to the sustainability and replication phase by providing suitable market segments and concrete districts for offering the solutions developed in PEDvolution. These results can be directly used by tool developers and other actors to start their exploitation activities beyond the project duration.

Figure 10: Planned activities after the end of PEDvolution

10.2 Partners' expected contributions and detailed work plan

10.2.1 *Partners' roles and responsibilities*

PEDvolution partners have specific responsibilities when it comes to C&D&E activities, which align with each organisation's expertise and competencies. This approach allows each partner to contribute to the dissemination and exploitation of project results in an appropriate and efficient manner. These roles are described in the present section in accordance with the GA and Consortium Agreement (CA) requirements.

C&D&E MANAGER

Experience in the planning, management and coordination of C&D&E actions and strategies with a socio-environmental focus, as well as knowledge of the specific procedures is necessary when it comes to undertaking the role of the C&D&E Manager within the scope of EU-funded projects. For PEDvolution, SXS has been assigned with this role. Specifically, SXS is responsible for the timely implementation of the following:

- Development of the PEDvolution Plan for Exploitation & Dissemination
- Creation of the project identity, dissemination materials and channels
- Supporting a strong presence of the project, online and on-location
- Development and ensuring that the Monitoring & Tracking tool is kept updated
- Ensure materials and processes follows the required Programme guidelines
- Facilitation of smooth coordination and implementation of the C&D&E activities
- Report to INLE of the respective activities throughout the project duration
- Report to INLE in view of the EC reporting process foreseen to be submitted to CINEA

PROJECT COORDINATOR - IPR MANAGER

As PC INLE is responsible to ensure that any technical content included in the C&D&E material, is in line with the project's technical objectives (as defined in the project's Project Management Plan (D13.1)). For this purpose, INLE will review, fine-tune and contribute to the development of more technical content if required.

As part of the PC role to ensure timely delivery and implementation of activities, INLE will be kept up to date on important internal communications between partners and in case of conflict, which is not resolved directly by the WPL, INLE will intervene for further guidance in line with D13.1. Additionally, as IPR Manager, INLE will ensure that the agreed IPR protection procedures are respected. Finally, INLE will lead and supervise the successful outreach and liaising actions with BRIDGE, other relevant EU initiatives, as well other sister project or thematically relevant Horizon Europe projects (under T10.2, T11.3, T12.2).

WORK PACKAGE – TASK LEADERS

WPLs will be responsible to inform the C&D&E Manager, on the status, progress and completion of project results and deliverables, which can be disseminated via relevant communication channels to the PEDvolution target groups.

Specifically, for the project’s official public deliverables, each Lead Beneficiary (LB) will inform the C&D&E Manager on the status and expected delivery date, at least 3 weeks prior to the expected completion date, in line with the table below.

Table 14: PEDvolution Public Deliverables

DELIVERABLE	WP	LEAD BENEFICIARY	EXPECTED COMPLETION DATE (Mx)
Local community analysis and initial engagement plan	WP1	SIN	31 st October 2024 (M10)
Functional and operational requirements of the demo sites and Reference use cases	WP1	ICOM	31 st August 2024 (M8)
PED readiness assessment methodology	WP4	ZHAW	31 st December 2025 (M24)
PED Readiness Assessment Policy Strategy Roadmap	WP4	VITO	31 st December 2025 (M24)
PEDvolution decision support guideline application	WP4	ICOM	31 st December 2025 (M24)
Data exchange platform design	WP7	ICOM	31 st December 2024 (M12)
Data exchange platform and connection with EU Data Spaces	WP7	ICOM	31 st December 2025 (M24)
PEDs Monitoring and Verification Plan and Co-developer demos preparation	WP8	ESG	30 th November 2025 (M23)
Demonstrator acquisition process	WP8	INLE	31 st October 2025 (M22)
Demonstrator solution testing	WP9	SWW	31 st October 2026 (M34)
PEDs performance assessment report	WP9	ESG	31 st December 2026 (M36)
Plan for Exploitation and Dissemination	WP10	SXS	30 th June 2024 (M6)
Communication and dissemination activities – year 1	WP10	SXS	31 st December 2024 (M12)
Communication and dissemination activities – year 2	WP11	SXS	31 st December 2025 (M24)
KERs and characterisation	WP11	SXS	31 st December 2025 (M24)
Communication and dissemination activities – year 3	WP12	SXS	31 st December 2026 (M36)
PEDvolution replication and market analysis & exploitation strategy	WP12	TUW	31 st December 2026 (M36)

D10.1. Plan for Exploitation and Dissemination

Work Packages 6 and 9 are of vital importance for the exploitation efforts. Within the scope of WP6 “PED Business and social innovation tools”, and given their extensive experience in European projects, high quality network involved in energy transition and long track record, SIN will lead the adaption of the business model innovation tool and the social innovation tool to meet the specific needs of the demo PEDs. The implementation of the locally customised tools will start by actively engaging and interacting with PEDs, local stakeholders, and technology and solution providers through human-centred, participatory processes, thereby contributing significantly to PEDvolution exploitation efforts.

Within WP9 “PEDvolution demonstrators and performance assessment” led by SWW, and specifically T9.3 “PEDs performance assessment”, led by ZHAW, will also contribute significantly to exploitation efforts. Technical, social and business tools and results achieved in the WP2-7 will be assessed and evaluated according to the requirements defined in WP1 “User-centered system analysis” and the PED Readiness Assessment developed in WP4 “PED Readiness Assessment”. This task is of core importance to the maximisation of exploitation of KERs after comparing PED performance against the defined baselines.

Additionally, ZHAW as a member of ANNEX 83 and has been involved in its development, will support SXS in the standardisation and certification frameworks.

TUW as TL will be responsible for the development of task ST12.3.2 “Replication and market analysis” and the deliverable “PEDvolution replication and market analysis & exploitation strategy”.

PED MANAGERS AND SOLUTION PROVIDERS

Both PED Managers and Solution Providers will play an essential role in the exploitation of the PEDvolution results, the detailed strategy is to be developed within the scope of T12.3 when project results have matured.

PED Managers (SWW, ESG, EG, GEK, ZENOB, WIN) will have extensive experience with developing and evaluating PEDs, and as a result apart from the technical capacity, they also have a wide network which can significantly contribute to the dissemination and exploitation of project results and specifically as foreseen by their roles within WP6 “PED Business & social innovation tools” and WP9 “PEDvolution demonstrators and performance assessment” tasks. PED Managers are also aware of the advantages, technical difficulties and potential obstacles, and can therefore consult and guide other PED Managers on how they could benefit from the deployment of PEDvolution solutions in their respective district.

Solution Providers (OFFSET, ICOM, VITO, NTNU, ZHAW, TUW, SIN) have a track record on PED conceptualisation, implementation, and tool developments, as well as significant technical expertise, and a wide network within the R&D community. For this purpose, their contribution to the exploitation of project results during and after project completion is also essential.

ALL PARTNERS

All 15 partners will be involved in the C&D&E activities, for proper uptake and maximisation of exploitation potential and to ensure scalability and replication of results from innovative projects.

Partners will review and provide their feedback on the developed C&D&E materials in line with the internal review roles presented in D13.1. Specifically, regarding the translation of these materials, SXS will provide an initial translation in all national languages, which will then be reviewed and fine-tuned as required by partners before being considered final. In case one national language corresponds to more than one partner, the final version will need to be approved by all partners.

D10.1. Plan for Exploitation and Dissemination

Partners will also be actively involved in the provision of material which can be used to update the project website and/or create social media posts, news alerts, press releases or respective dissemination material by the C&D&E Manager. In order to ensure smooth and effective implementation of this task, partners will provide input via the Tracking and Monitoring tool in line with [Table 15](#) below.

Table 15: Provision of input for the PEDvolution dissemination channels

DATE (Mx)	PARTNER	DATE (Mx)	PARTNER
20 th June 2024 (M6)	SXS	20 th October 2025 (M22)	INLE
19 th July 2024 (M7)	INLE	20 th November 2025 (M23)	VITO
20 th August 2024 (M8)	VITO	19 th December 2025 (M24)	SIN
20 th September 2024 (M9)	SIN	20 th January 2026 (M25)	NTNU
21 st October 2024 (M10)	NTNU	20 th February 2026 (M26)	OFFSET
20 th November 2024 (M11)	OFFSET	20 th March 2026 (M27)	SWW
20 th December 2024 (M12)	SWW	20 th April 2026 (M28)	ESG
20 th January 2025 (M13)	ESG	20 th May 2026 (M29)	TUW
20 th February 2025 (M14)	TUW	19 th June 2026 (M30)	ICOM
20 th March 2025 (M15)	ICOM	20 th July 2026 (M31)	EG
21 st April 2025 (M16)	EG	20 th August 2026 (M32)	GEK
20 th May 2025 (M17)	GEK	21 st September 2026 (M33)	ZENOB
20 th June 2025 (M18)	ZENOB	20 th October 2026 (M34)	ZHAW
21 st July 2025 (M19)	ZHAW	20 th November 2026 (M35)	WIN
20 th August 2025 (M20)	WIN	21 st December 2026 (M36)	SXS
19 th September 2025 (M21)	SXS		

Furthermore, throughout the project's lifetime, it is expected that all partners take advantage of every suitable opportunity to disseminate project progress and results both via online channels (organisation's website, social media pages) and via participation in 3rd party events in line with the specifications in [Section 7.1](#). All partners should aim to present PEDvolution in at least one national or regional event, while for EU-level and international events partners' involvement is expected in line with the table below.

D10.1. Plan for Exploitation and Dissemination

Table 16: Partners' attendance in EU-International 3rd party events

	NO. OF EU 3 RD PARTY EVENTS	INVOLVED PARTNERS
Year 1	n/a	n/a
Year 2	1	SXS, VITO, SIN, ZHAW, WIN
Year 3	2	SXS, INLE, VITO, SIN, ZHAW, WIN

Finally, PEDvolution partners will regularly track their dissemination efforts, updating SXS as C&D&E Manager on a regular basis using the Monitoring & Tracking tool as described in [Chapter 13](#).

The detailed C&D&E work plan for Work Packages 10 - 12 is presented in the following section.

10.2.2 Detailed Work Plan WP10-12

		2024											
		1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
WP10: Communication & Dissemination Tasks (Year 1)		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
T10.1	Communication tools and materials (M1-M12)	J	F	M	A	M	J	J	A	S	O	N	D
ST10.1.1	<i>Development of communication & dissemination strategy & plan (M1-M6) (SXS)</i>												
ST10.1.2	<i>Development of project identity, applications and basic documentation (M1-M12) (SXS)</i>												
	Project Templates for reports/agenda/minutes/presentation & avatars												
	Project Logo												
	Roll-up banner (ENG version)												
	Roll-up banner (National versions) (SXS/ALL)												
	Brochure (ENG version)												
	Brochure (National versions) (SXS/ALL)												
	Poster (ENG version)												
	Poster (National versions) (SXS/ALL)												
	Presentation and factsheet in EN												
ST10.1.3	<i>Project online presence (website, hubs, social) (M1 - M12) (SXS/ALL)</i>												
	Website												
	Website updates												
	Social media (LinkedIn, Twitter, Youtube)												
	Social media updates												
	Digital Hubs												
	Digital News Alerts												
	GDRP contacts database												
T10.2	Liaison with BRIDGE and other EU initiatives (M1-M12)	J	F	M	A	M	J	J	A	S	O	N	D
ST10.2.1	<i>Liaison with other projects and consortia, BRIDGE initiative, including AIOTI, Annex83, COST Action on PEDS (M1 - M12) (INLE)</i>												
ST10.2.1	<i>Participation in BRIDGE General Assembly (M4) (INLE)</i>												

D10.1. Plan for Exploitation and Dissemination

		2025											
		2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2
WP11: Project Communication, Dissemination and further Exploitation (Year 2)		13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24
T11.1	Communication of the project and Dissemination of results - Year 2 (M13-24)	J	F	M	A	M	J	J	A	S	O	N	D
ST11.1.1	<i>EU dissemination events and networks (SXS/ALL)</i>												
ST11.1.2	<i>National dissemination events and networks (SXS/ALL)</i>												
ST11.1.3	<i>Project online presence updates (SXS/ALL)</i>												
	Website updates												
	Social media account updates												
	Digital Hub updates												
	News Alerts												
ST11.1.4	<i>Other communication material (SXS)</i>												
	Advertorial video												
T11.2	KERs update and characterisation (M13-24)	J	F	M	A	M	J	J	A	S	O	N	D
T11.2	<i>Identification and updating of Key Exploitable Results (SXS/PED Managers)</i>												
T11.3	Liaison with BRIDGE and other EU initiatives (M13-24)	J	F	M	A	M	J	J	A	S	O	N	D
T11.3	<i>Liaison with BRIDGE and other EU initiatives (M13-24) (INLE/VITO, SIN, ICOM, ZHAW, SWW, ESG)</i>												

D10.1. Plan for Exploitation and Dissemination

		2026											
		3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3
WP12: Project Communication, Dissemination and further Exploitation (Year 3) (M25-M36)		25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33	34	35	36
T12.1	Communication of the project and Dissemination of results-Year 3 (M25-36)	J	F	M	A	M	J	J	A	S	O	N	D
ST12.1.1	<i>EU dissemination events and networks – Final Conference (SXS/ ALL)</i>												
	Participation in EU dissemination event												
	Final Conference												
	4 Scientific Publications												
ST12.1.2	<i>National dissemination events and networks (SXS/ ALL)</i>												
ST12.1.3	<i>Project online presence updates (SXS/ ALL)</i>												
	Website updates												
	News Alerts												
	Social media account updates												
	Hub updates												
ST12.1.4	Other communication material - Layman's report (SXS)												
T12.2	Liaison with BRIDGE and other EU initiatives (M25-36)	J	F	M	A	M	J	J	A	S	O	N	D
T12.2	Liaison with BRIDGE and other EU initiatives (M25-36) (INLE/VITO, SIN, ICOM, ZHAW, SWW, ESG)												
T12.3	Sustainability plan, exploitation and replication (M25-M36)	J	F	M	A	M	J	J	A	S	O	N	D
ST12.3.1	<i>Joint and Individual exploitation strategy for most promising KERs (SXS/ALL)</i>												
ST12.3.2	<i>Replication and market analysis (TUW)</i>												
	Identification of key success criteria												
	Set-up a database												
	Assess possible evolution of criteria												
	Assess potential to replicate PEDvolution solutions												

Figure 12: PEDvolution detailed work plan for WP10 - 12

11 GUIDANCE FOR THE USE OF MEDIA

The support of the specialist media is important for the project's communication and dissemination since they are catalysts for greater awareness and impact.

This kind of material (such as press releases) is developed or adapted when/as considered appropriate, in order to be published or broadcasted for free, in the form of news, interview, or commentary and not of commercial advertising.

The media can decide whether it is worth publishing/broadcasting or not. What we can do to increase the possibilities of our material reaching the audience, is:

- ❖ The material must be delivered to the right person in each media organisation. This is handled through the project's database, including media contacts. The contacts' information must be confirmed, and the delivery must be done in time.
- ❖ The material must be interesting and appealing to the media's audience, so it is considered worth to be presented by the media. It must be as short as possible, "juicy", "digestible" and easy to understand, using simple language and attractive supportive material (photos, graphs, infographics, videos etc.).
- ❖ The material must be formatted in a way to make it easy for the journalist/producer to use it, requiring the minimum effort from him/her for processing. It must include a well and properly formatted text, adapted to the medium's audience and style, and sufficient and attractive supportive material, such as photos, images, video etc.
- ❖ It must be aligned with the media's terms and limits, so it is assured it will not cause any kind of conflict with parts of the audience. In addition, it must not cause conflicts with the media itself (such as advertising issues, e.g., related to companies from the industry advertising on the media).

In this case, the press releases' production will be handled by SXS with the support of INLE as the PC (regarding central messages and information intended for distribution in the individual markets) and of the local partners responsible for the pilot markets (regarding local messages and information about the specific pilot market).

The local partners will take care of the final distribution, follow up and evaluation of publications on the local media. The contact information of these local media will be supported by the contacts database, stored by the local partners.

12 KEY PERFORMANCE INDICATORS

The following quantitative Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) have been defined as a means to evaluate PEDvolution's impact and outreach in terms of communication and dissemination. The project's impact will be closely monitored throughout the project lifecycle, allowing for remedial actions if required. For this purpose, indicative unique KPIs per year have also been defined in the table below.

Table 17: PEDvolution C&D&E Metrics and Targets & Indicative breakdown per year

INDICATOR	TARGET	INDICATOR	TARGET
Website unique visitors	>10000	Twitter followers	>1000
<i>Website unique visitors (Year 1)</i>	>1500	<i>Twitter followers (Year 1)</i>	>200
<i>Website unique visitors (Year 2)</i>	>4000	<i>Twitter followers (Year 2)</i>	>400
<i>Website unique visitors (Year 3)</i>	>4500	<i>Twitter followers (Year 3)</i>	>400
INDICATOR	TARGET	INDICATOR	TARGET
Website page views	>30000	Representation in EU events	>3
<i>Website page views (Year 1)</i>	>5000	<i>Representation in EU events (Year 1)</i>	-
<i>Website page views (Year 2)</i>	>10000	<i>Representation in EU events (Year 2)</i>	2
<i>Website page views (Year 3)</i>	>15000	<i>Representation in EU events (Year 3)</i>	1
INDICATOR	TARGET	INDICATOR	TARGET
Report downloads	>8000	Representation in national/regional events	>5
<i>Report downloads (Year 1)</i>	>300	<i>Representation in national/regional events (Year 1)</i>	-
<i>Report downloads (Year 2)</i>	>3000	<i>Representation in national/regional events (Year 2)</i>	>2
<i>Report downloads (Year 3)</i>	>4700	<i>Representation in national/regional events (Year 3)</i>	>3
INDICATOR	TARGET	INDICATOR	TARGET
Video views	>2000	Final conference participants	>120
<i>Video views (Year 1)</i>	-		
<i>Video views (Year 2)</i>	>500		

D10.1. Plan for Exploitation and Dissemination

Video views (Year 3)	>1500		Final conference participants (Year 3)	>120
INDICATOR				
TARGET		INDICATOR		TARGET
Project outreach contacts	>2000		News Alerts recipients	>1000
Project outreach contacts (Year 1)	>500		News Alerts recipients (Year 1)	>500
Project outreach contacts (Year 2)	>700		News Alerts recipients (Year 2)	>700
Project outreach contacts (Year 3)	>800		News Alerts recipients (Year 3)	>800
INDICATOR				
TARGET		INDICATOR		TARGET
Posts to digital hubs	>10		News Alerts issues	>6
Posts to digital hubs (Year 1)	>3		News Alerts issues (Year 1)	>2
Posts to digital hubs (Year 2)	>3		News Alerts issues (Year 2)	>2
Posts to digital hubs (Year 3)	>4		News Alerts issues (Year 3)	>2
INDICATOR				
TARGET		INDICATOR		TARGET
Social networks original posts	>100		News Alert open rate	>30%
Social networks original posts (Year 1)	>30		News Alert open rate (Year 1)	>30%
Social networks original posts (Year 2)	>30		News Alert open rate (Year 2)	>30%
Social networks original posts (Year 3)	>40		News Alert open rate (Year 3)	>30%
INDICATOR				
TARGET		INDICATOR		TARGET
LinkedIn followers	>500		Scientific publications	>5
LinkedIn followers (Year 1)	>100		Scientific publications (Year 1)	-
LinkedIn followers (Year 2)	>200		Scientific publications (Year 2)	>2
LinkedIn followers (Year 3)	>200		Scientific publications (Year 3)	>3

13 MONITORING AND TRACKING

13.1 Procedure and Partners' roles

The monitoring and tracking of C&D&E activities is of vital importance, to ensure smooth implementation of the foreseen tasks in line with the requirements of the Horizon Europe programme, but also to safeguard adequate reporting.

For this purpose, SXS as the C&D&E Manager is responsible for setting the procedures and the overall monitoring of the respective activities. As mentioned in [Section 10.2.3](#), a report is foreseen to be developed at the end of each year, summarising the implemented activities and achievements (D10.2, D11.1, D12.1).

For the same purpose and in order to facilitate this process, SXS has developed a monitoring tool shared with all partners on [Microsoft Teams Sharepoint \(See Annex IV\)](#). The tool captures both the **reporting procedure** and simultaneously supports the provision of the **input collection process** for the regular updating of the online communication tools. For conformity and facilitation purpose, all project reporting process related to WP10 -12 will be conducted via this tool.

Below are some points partners need to consider when updating the tool:

- ❖ For the reporting section, all partners are required to report on achieved activities, by updating tabs "**Communication activities**", "**Dissemination activities**", "**Scientific Publications**" and "**Popularised publications**" on a monthly basis or when relevant material is available. Relevant reminders will be sent out by the C&D&E Manager for this purpose.
- ❖ INLE as TL of activities T10.2, T11.3, T12.2 should also complete the "**Liaison with EU-initiatives**" tab at least on a bi-annual basis and at the end of each reporting period.
- ❖ SXS will complete the "**KPIs reporting**" tab at the end of each reporting period, with the contribution from project partners, where deemed necessary (as described in the points above).
- ❖ All partners are also expected to contribute to the implementation of communication and dissemination activities by providing input for the website, social media (Twitter and LinkedIn) and for the News Alerts by updating the **0.Input form (Website-SM-NA)** tab on a monthly basis in line with [Table 15](#) or whenever interesting material is available. Additionally, when deliverables/important outputs/results are available and milestones are achieved, the sheet should be completed by the responsible partner (Lead Beneficiary). Relevant reminders will be sent out by the C&D&E Manager for this purpose.
- ❖ It is important to always first refer to the "Activities Categorisation" table on the right side of the "**Instructions**" tab); this is a guide so to confirm where (under which tab, i.e. either "**Communication activities**" or "**Dissemination activities**") to record it.
- ❖ Partners should always make sure to make any modifications/changes directly on the version uploaded on [Microsoft Teams Sharepoint](#).

14 CONCLUSION

The PEDvolution partners will collaborate closely and efficiently throughout the project duration, towards maximising dissemination and exploitation efforts and achieving maximum impact for results and outputs. This will require strong accountability and engagement from all project partners, as well as the C&D&E Manager.

This deliverable aims to guide the implementation of the project's communication, dissemination and exploitation activities, and should be used as a reference point to ensure their smooth implementation. More specifically, the deliverable presents the specific communication & dissemination objectives, tasks, roles and responsibilities for the PEDvolution partners in order to achieve the defined goals and KPIs. The activities will be closely monitored, and the results will be presented in the respective yearly reports. During the final year of implementation, when project results have matured, a detailed joint and individual strategy will be developed for the exploitation of the most promising KERs. The document will be updated as required during project implementation.

Chapter 2 defines the purpose of this plan and the project's C&D&E objectives. Chapter 3 sets out the C&D&E context, means and strategic approach, while Chapter 4 presents the project's target groups, their main characteristics, classification and relevance to communication, dissemination and exploitation activities.

Chapter 5 introduces the project's key messages and communication elements, whereas Chapter 6 analytically describes the communication and dissemination tools to be implemented during the project duration. Chapter 7 deals with expert communication & dissemination activities in which PEDvolution partners are expected to participate, the final PEDvolution conference and the collaboration with other EU initiatives. Chapter 8 considers the KERs and exploitation pathways, while Chapter 9 deals with the concept of exploitation in market and policy as well as project sustainability. Chapter 10 details the work plan related with Work Packages 10, 11 & 12, as well as partners' roles and expected contributions in the C&D&E activities. Chapter 11 includes guidelines for the use of media to be considered by partners and Chapter 12 summarises the C&D&E KPIs and defines an indicative breakdown for each KPI per year. Finally, Chapter 13, explains the need for monitoring and tracking of C&D&E activities and presents guidelines for partners the use of the tracking tool.

15 REFERENCES

15.1 Definition of basic terms

- ❖ **Communication:** Taking strategic and targeted measures for promoting the action itself and its results to a multitude of audiences, including the media and the public, and possibly engaging in a two-way exchange. (Source: *HE Programme Guide, 2024*)
- ❖ **Dissemination:** The public disclosure of the results by appropriate means (other than resulting from protecting or exploiting the results) including by scientific publications in any medium. (Source: *HE Programme Guide, 2024*)
- ❖ **Exploitation:** The use of results in further research and innovation activities other than those covered by the action concerned, including among other things, commercial exploitation such as developing, creating, manufacturing, and marketing a product or process, creating and providing a service, or in standardisation activities. (Source: *HE Programme Guide, 2024*)
- ❖ **Impacts:** Wider long-term effects on society (including the environment), the economy and science, enabled by the outcomes of R&I investments (long term). It refers to the specific contribution of the project to the work program expected impacts described in the destination. Impacts generally occur sometime after the end of the project. (Source: *HE Programme Guide, 2024*)
- ❖ **Positive Energy District:** Energy-efficient and energy-flexible urban areas which produce net zero greenhouse gas emissions and actively manage an annual local or regional surplus production of renewable energy. They require integration of different systems and infrastructures and interaction between buildings, the users and the regional energy, mobility and ICT systems, while optimising the livability of the urban environment in line with social, economic and environmental sustainability. (Source: *Reference Framework for Positive Energy Districts and Neighbourhoods, Urban Europe, 2020*)
- ❖ **PED Genotype:** The set of genetic material, built through a unique combination of social-technology-interopability-market related aspects. (Source: *PEDvolution DoA, Part A*)
- ❖ **PED Phenotype:** The set of observable characteristics of the PED resulting from the interaction of its genotype with the environment (e.g. energy market, industry, mobility, (geo)politics). (Source: *PEDvolution DoA, Part A*)
- ❖ **Results:** What is generated during the project implementation. This may include, for example, know-how, innovative solutions, algorithms, proof of feasibility, new business models, policy recommendations, guidelines, prototypes, demonstrators, databases and datasets, trained researchers, new infrastructures, networks, etc. Most project results (inventions, scientific works etc.) are “Intellectual Property”, which may if appropriate, be protected by formal “Intellectual Property Rights”. (Source: *HE Programme Guide, 2024*)

N.B: Section to be updated as required.

15.2 Sources

- [1] [Factsheet](#): 97% of buildings in the EU need to be upgraded, BPIE
- [2] [Horizon Europe Programme Guide, May 2024](#)
- [3] https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/docs/h2020-funding-guide/grants/grant-management/dissemination-of-results_en.htm
- [4] https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/strategy/dissemination-and-exploitation-research-results_en
- [5] [Manual for recipients of SERI funding](#)
- [6] Osterwalder, Alexander; Pigneur, Yves; Clark, Tim (2010): Business Model Generation: A Handbook For Visionaries, Game Changers, and Challengers. Strategyzer series. Hoboken, NJ: John Wiley & Sons. ISBN 9780470876411. OCLC 648031756
- [7] Reference Framework for Positive Energy Districts and Neighbourhoods, Urban Europe, 2020
- [8] [SERI Communication & Dissemination manual](#)

ANNEX I: PROJECT IDENTITY AND APPLICATIONS

PROJECT LOGO WITH TAGLINE

PROJECT LOGO WITHOUT TAGLINE

PRESENTATION TEMPLATE

The presentation template features a central image of a modern building with a glass facade, surrounded by several hexagonal shapes in teal, orange, and light blue. The layout includes the following elements:

- Logo:** PEDvolution logo with the tagline "Interoperable solutions to streamline PED evolution and cross-sectoral integration".
- Title:** Title of presentation up to 4 lines.
- Presenter:** Name of presenter, affiliation, Event, Date, location.
- Funding:** Co-funded by the European Union (under grant agreement N° 101138472). Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or CINEA. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.
- Swiss Confederation:** Schweizerische Eidgenossenschaft, Confédération suisse, Confederazione Svizzera, Confederaziun svizra, Swiss Confederation.
- Swiss State Secretariat:** Federal Department of Economic Affairs, Education and Research EAER, State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation SERI.
- Disclaimer:** The Swiss project participants received funding from the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SERI).

REPORT/DELIVERABLE TEMPLATE

Deliverable No
Deliverable Title

**Co-funded by
the European Union**

Schweizerische Eidgenossenschaft
Confédération suisse
Confederazione Svizzera
Confederaziun Svizra
Swiss Confederation

Federal Department of Economic Affairs,
Education and Research E.A.R.
State Secretariat for Education,
Research and Innovation SERI

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement N° 101138472.

The Swiss project participants received funding from the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SERI).

DX.X. Deliverable Title

Document Summary Information

Grant Agreement No	101138472	Acronym	PEDvolution
Full Title	Interoperable solutions to streamline PED evolution and cross-sectoral integration		
Start Date	01/01/2024	Duration	36 months
Project URL	https://www.pedvolution.eu/		
Deliverable			
Work Package			
Contractual due date		Actual submission date	
Nature		Dissemination Level	
Lead Beneficiary			
Responsible Author	Fullname (Partner organisation)		
Contributions from	Fullname (Partner organisation)		
Reviewed by	Fullname (Partner organisation)		

Copyright message
©PEDvolution Consortium 2024. This document comprises entirely original and unreleased content unless explicitly stated otherwise. Recognition of previously published material and the contributions of others has been expressed through suitable citation, quotation, or both. Reproduction is permitted, with acknowledgment of the source.

Disclaimer
PEDvolution - This project has received funding from the Horizon Europe Framework Programme (HORIZON) under the GA No. 101138472. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or CINEA. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them. The European Commission holds no responsibility for any potential utilisation of the information it contains. The information is presented "as is" with no assurance or warranty, whether explicit or implicit, regarding its suitability for any specific purpose. The user assumes sole responsibility and risk when using this information.

© PEDvolution, 2024 Page | 2

MEETING AGENDA AND MINUTES TEMPLATE

PEDvolution
Interoperable solutions to streamline
PED evolution and cross-sectoral integration

Title:
Date:
Time:
Location:

#	Activity Detail	Start Time	Duration	End Time	Speaker
1					
2					
2					
3					
	End of Meeting				

Additional Information

Title of the Occasion

3 DISCUSSION NOTES SUMMARY

ITEM No	SUBJECT/DESCRIPTION <small>(aligned with agenda items)</small>	RESULT ¹	RESPONSIBLE PERSON/PARTNER	DUE DATE

© PEDvolution, 2024
Page | 5

WEB DESIGN ELEMENTS

NEWS ALERTS TEMPLATE

NEWS ALERT 2024 06

PEDvolution Partners meet in Athens, Greece - The Journey begins!

The 1st PEDvolution General Assembly took place in Athens on 27th and 28th of February 2024. During the two-day event, partners discussed project objectives, the progress made so far particularly on the technical work packages, and planned upcoming tasks.

[Full Story](#)

PEDvolution at the BRIDGE annual General Assembly meeting

It was a great honour for PEDvolution to participate in the BRIDGE annual General Assembly meeting, which took place in Brussels on 9th and 10th of April 2024, with a total of 190 projects being represented.

Three PEDvolution partners –INLECOM, Smart Innovation Norway and INTRACOM– attended the event and had the opportunity to engage in insightful discussions, connect and exchange with fellow innovators, establishing the ground for collaboration and exchange of expertise.

[Full Story](#)

**Co-funded by
the European Union**

This project has received funding from the Horizon Europe Framework Programme (HORIZON) under Grant Agreement No. 101138452. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or CINEA. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Administration fédérale suisse
de l'éducation, de la recherche
et de l'innovation
SERI
Rue du Commerce 44
CH-1015 Lausanne
Téléphone: +41 22 319 1111
www.seri.ch

The Swiss project participants have received funding from the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SERI).

SOCIAL MEDIA IDENTITY HEADERS & AVATARS

ANNEX II: PRINTABLE MATERIALS

BROCHURE

CONTEXT & CHALLENGE

- The built environment is key to Europe's transition to a climate-neutral society by 2050.
- An estimated 97% of dwellings are not fit for this purpose. A clean energy system and a just transition require more than isolated technological solutions for individual buildings.
- To optimally decarbonise the urban environment, it is crucial to implement fully interoperable solutions at the neighbourhood level, that improve energy efficiency and integrate local renewable energy sources and excess heat more effectively.
- A Positive Energy District (PED) is an urban area that produces at least as much energy on an annual basis as it consumes.

Discover PEDvolution

Project start date: 01/01/2024
Duration: 36 months

7 countries
15 organisations

Total Budget: 4.3 million €

Would you like to learn more about PEDvolution?
Are you interested in Positive Energy Districts?
Get in touch with us through our website!

@PEDvolutionEU | PEDvolution

www.pedvolution.eu

ACCOMMODATING THE CONSTANT EVOLUTION OF POSITIVE ENERGY DISTRICTS

Interoperable solutions to streamline Positive Energy District evolution and cross-sectoral integration

Co-funded by the European Union

The project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101019718. The content of this document does not necessarily reflect the views of the European Union or the European Commission, and the European Union is not responsible for any use of the information contained therein.

PARTNERS

ASSOCIATED ENTITIES

THE OPPORTUNITY

PEDs are the backbone of urban energy ecosystems. They can improve energy efficiency, integrate local renewable energy sources and excess heat more effectively, and enable interaction with the energy & non-energy sectors such as mobility, ICT and industry.

A crucial, often neglected fact is that PEDs are in constant evolution due to ever-evolving changes in their environment, including social context, legislation, energy market, technologies, energy prices. As such, there is a strong analogy with the theory of evolution.

Still, the DNA of PEDs varies, and the implementation & evolution of different PEDs, as well as their probability of success in the urban energy transition, is determined by the environment.

7 INTEROPERABLE SOLUTIONS

- PED Design and Planning Toolkit
- PED Energy Manager
- PED Social Innovation tool
- PED Readiness Assessment
- Dynamic Decision Support Dashboard for PED Development
- Data Exchange, Integration and Interoperability Platform
- PED Business Model Innovation Tool Platform

SPECIFIC NEEDS

- Improve energy efficiency coupled with a better integration of local renewables and local excess heat sources within the districts.
- Increase citizen participation and integration of consumers and energy communities in the value chain of the energy system.
- Improve cross-sectoral integration on energy and non-energy sectors within PEDs.
- Demonstrate fully interoperable solutions for planning, design, development, and management of PEDs.

EXPECTED RESULTS

- Increased availability of tools, guides and interoperable solutions for planning, design, development, and management of PEDs.
- Improved integration of energy and non-energy sectors within PEDs.
- Improved integration of PEDs in energy systems and improved contribution of PEDs to energy grid robustness regarding dependencies to energy supplies.
- Increased social entrepreneurship and citizen participation and engagement in energy communities.
- Increased participation of consumers and energy communities in the value chain of the energy system.

3 PED CO-DEVELOPER DEMONSTRATORS

Schönbrunn village, Wunsiedel, Germany

- In Operation
- 6,709,386.4 m²
- 1,230 residents
- 400 households & 9 businesses

Relevant PEDvolution Partners: SSW, ZENOS, ESG

Residential neighbourhood, Pjanina, Kranj, Slovenia

- In planning stage
- 6,709,386.4 m²
- 740,000 m²
- 16,000 residents
- 4,300 apartments & 40 businesses

Relevant PEDvolution Partners: EG, G&K

Gemeinschaft Hard, Winterthur, Switzerland

- In Operation
- 80,000 m²
- 250 residents
- 45 apartments & 40 businesses

Relevant PEDvolution Partners: WIK, ZHAW

TARGET GROUPS

- Energy service providers & Mobility service providers
- Residents/Energy consumers
- Energy Prosumers
- PED developers and managers
- PED Investors
- Local Authorities and City planners
- Policy makers & Standardization bodies
- Research & Academia
- Specialist media

PED PHENOTYPE vs **PED GENOTYPE**

The PEDvolution solutions will design, process, optimise and strengthen the PEDs genotype and/or phenotype.

The genotype of a PED is its set of genetic material, built through a unique combination of Social-Technology-Interoperability-Market related aspects.

The PED's phenotype is the set of observable characteristics resulting from the interaction of its genotype with the environment.

POSTER

PEDvolution
Interoperable solutions to streamline Positive Energy District evolution and cross-sectoral integration

ACCOMMODATING THE CONSTANT EVOLUTION OF PEDs

CONTEXT

Positive Energy Districts (PEDs) are the pinnacle of urban energy ecosystems. They can improve energy efficiency, integrate local renewable energy sources & excess heat more effectively and enable interaction with the **energy & non-energy sectors, like mobility & ICT**.

A crucial, often neglected, fact is that PEDs are in constant **evolution**, due to ever-evolving changes in their environment, including **social context, legislation, energy market, technologies and energy prices**.

Still the **DNA** of PEDs varies and the implementation & evolution of different PEDs, as well as their probability of success in the urban energy transition, is determined by the **environment**.

OBJECTIVES – SPECIFIC NEEDS

Improve energy efficiency coupled with a better integration of local renewables and local excess heat sources within the districts.

Increase citizen participation and integration of consumers and energy communities in the value chain of the energy system.

Improve cross-sectorial integration on energy and non-energy sectors within PEDs (between buildings, the users and the regional energy, mobility & ICT systems).

Demonstrate **fully interoperable solutions** for planning, design, development and management of PEDs.

PED CO-DEVELOPER DEMONSTRATORS

Schönbrunn village Wunsiedel, Germany

Residential neighbourhood Planina, Kranj, Slovenia

Gemeinschaft Hard, Winterthur, Switzerland

7 SOLUTIONS

PEDvolution paves the way for cross-sectoral integration of ever-evolving PEDs, through the co-development and implementation of 7 interoperable solutions.

PED Design and Planning Toolkit

Dynamic Decision Support Guideline for PED Development

PED Energy Manager

Data Exchange, Integration and Interoperability Platform

PED Readiness Assessment

PED Business Models

PED Social Innovation Tool

EXPECTED OUTCOMES

1. **Increased availability of tools, guides and interoperable solutions** for planning, design, development and management of PEDs.
2. **Improved integration of energy** (e.g. distributed renewable energy generation, waste heat utilisation, storage) and **non-energy sectors** (e.g. mobility) within PEDs.
3. **Improved integration of PEDs in energy systems** and improved contribution of PEDs to energy grid robustness regarding dependencies to energy supplies.
4. **Increased social entrepreneurship and citizen participation and engagement** in energy communities.
5. **Increased participation of consumers and energy communities** in the **value chain** of the energy system.

Project start date: 01/01/2024

Duration: 36 months

7 countries

15 organisations

Total EU Budget: 4.9 million €

PARTNERS

ASSOCIATED ENTITIES

Co-funded by the European Union

This project has received funding from the Horizon Europe Framework Programme (HORIZON) under Grant Agreement No. 101018812. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the authors only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or ERDF. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Schweizerische Eidgenossenschaft
Confédération suisse
Confederazione Svizzera
Confederaziun svizra

Swiss Confederation

The Swiss project participants have received funding from the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SERI).

www.pedvolution.eu

[@PEDvolutionEU](https://twitter.com/PEDvolutionEU) [in PEDvolution](https://www.linkedin.com/company/pedvolution)

ROLL-UP BANNER

PEDvolution

Interoperable solutions to streamline Positive Energy District evolution and cross-sectoral integration

PED PHENOTYPE

PED GENOTYPE

Accommodating the constant evolution of PEDs

CONTEXT

Positive Energy Districts (PEDs) are the pinnacle of urban energy ecosystems. They can improve energy efficiency, integrate local renewable energy sources & excess heat more effectively and enable interaction with the **energy & non-energy sectors, like mobility & ICT**.

A crucial, often neglected, fact is that PEDs are in constant **evolution**, due to **ever-evolving** changes in their environment, including **social context, legislation, energy market, technologies and energy prices**. As such there is a strong analogy with the theory of evolution.

Still the **DNA** of PEDs varies and the implementation & evolution of different PEDs, as well as their probability of success in the urban energy transition, is determined by the **environment**.

SOLUTIONS

PEDvolution paves the way for cross-sectoral integration of ever-evolving PEDs. European pioneers in PED conceptualisation, implementation and tool development, will materialise this through the co-development and implementation of seven interoperable solutions accommodating the constant evolution of PEDs.

PED Design and Planning Toolkit

Dynamic Decision Support Guidelines for PED Development

PED Energy Manager

Data Exchange, Integration and Interoperability Platforms

PED Readiness Assessment

PED Business Models

PED Social Innovation Tool

The solutions will evaluate and improve the **PED Readiness Level** according to the four genes of the **PED genotype: social, technology, interoperability and market**, which in their turn are influenced by their interaction within the PED and its environment (**PED phenotype**).

PED CO-DEVELOPER DEMONSTRATORS

Schönbunn in Sage Wuzsiedel, Germany

Residential neighbourhood Marina, Kranj, Slovenia

Gemeinshaft Hard, Winterthur, Switzerland

PARTNERS

ASSOCIATED ENTITIES

Co-funded by the European Union

The content of this document represents the views of the author(s) only and does not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the European Commission can be held responsible for any use of the information contained herein.

The information contained herein is confidential and intended solely for the individual named herein. It is not to be disseminated outside the named individual or organisation.

@PEDvolutionEU PEDvolution www.pedvolution.eu

ANNEX III: DIGITAL PRESENTATION

PEDvolution | PROJECT OVERVIEW, VISION & EXPECTED RESULTS

Name of presenter, affiliation

Event
Date, location

**Co-funded by
the European Union**

Co-funded by the European Union (under grant agreement N° 101138472). Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or CINEA. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Schweizerische Eidgenossenschaft
Confédération suisse
Confederazione Svizzera
Confederaziun svizra

Swiss Confederation

Federal Department of Economic Affairs,
Education and Research EAER
State Secretariat for Education,
Research and Innovation SERI

The Swiss project participants received funding from the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SERI).

PEDvolution CONCEPT (1/2)

PED PHENOTYPE

PED GENOTYPE

•**PED Genotype:** PED's set of genetic material, built through a unique combination of **Social-Technology-Interoperability-Market** related aspects.

•**PED Phenotype:** the set of observable characteristics of the PED resulting from the interaction of its genotype with the **environment** (e.g. energy market, industry, mobility, (geo)politics).

❖ The PEDvolution solutions will design, process, optimise and strengthen the PEDs genotype- and/or phenotype.

ANNEX IV: TRACKING & MONITORING TOOL

Communication & Dissemination activities Monitoring & Tracking tool (WP10 - WP12)

Co-funded by the European Union

ACTIVITIES - CATEGORISATION

Communication	Dissemination
Event (conference, meeting, workshop, internet debate, round table, group discussion, etc.)	Clustering activities
Exhibition	Collaboration with EU-funded projects
Interview	Conference
Media article	Education and training events
Newsletter	Meetings
Press release	Other scientific collaboration
Print materials (Brochure, leaflet, posters, stickers, banners, etc.)	Other
Social media	
TV/Radio campaign	
Video	
Website	
Other	

PURPOSE OF THIS TOOL

The aim of this tool is to support the smooth monitoring and tracking of PEDvolution's communication and dissemination activities as foreseen in WP 10 - WP12 in Annex 1 (DoA) Parts A & B of the Grant Agreement and according to the information required in the reporting template of the HORIZON EUROPE platform.

INSTRUCTIONS

- SYMPRAXIS (SXS)** is responsible for setting the procedures and the overall monitoring/tracking of the communication & dissemination activities.
- ALL PARTNERS** are expected to contribute to the implementation and monitoring of communication and dissemination activities by:
 - Providing input for the website, social media (Twitter and LinkedIn) and for the News Alerts by updating the 0.Input form (Website-SM-NA) tab on a monthly basis or whenever interesting material is available. Additionally, when deliverables/important outputs/results are available and milestones are achieved, the sheet should be completed by the responsible partner (Lead Beneficiary).
 - Reporting on up-coming or past activities in tabs "Communication activities", "Dissemination activities", "Scientific Publications" and "Popularised publications" on a monthly basis. (Relevant reminders will be sent out by the C&D&E Manager for this purpose.)
- INLECOM (INLE)** will complete the "Liaison with EU-initiatives" tab on a monthly basis and at the end of each reporting period.
- SXS** will complete the "KPIs reporting" tab at the end of each reporting period, with the contribution from project partners where appropriate (as described in points 2 & 3 above).
- When you plan to add an activity in this monitoring and tracking tool, please always first refer to the "Activities Categorisation" table on the right; this is your guide as to where (under which tab, i.e. either "Communication activities" or "Dissemination activities") to record it. In case of the "Events" category, please consider if the purpose of your participation has a communication or dissemination purpose. The categorisation is in line with the EC Portal options to facilitate reporting.
- When editing the document, please make sure to make any modifications/changes directly on the version uploaded on the **Sharepoint**.
- For more specific instructions on the completion of the document, refer to each separate sheet.

Instructions 0.Potential Participation Event 0.Input form (Website -SM-NA) **1.Communication activities** 2.Dissemination activities 3a.Scientific Publications 3b.Popularised Publications +

Activities	TARGETS*	1st reporting Actual	1st reporting %	2nd reporting Actual	2nd reporting %	Total for project duration	Total Project duration %
Project Website							
Number of Unique Visitors	10.000		0%		0%	0	0%
Number of pageviews	30.000		0%		0%	0	0%
Bounce rate <65%	65%		0%		0%	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!
Number of Report Downloads	8.000		0%		0%	0	0%
Video							
Number of Videos produced	1		0%		0%	0	0%
Number of Views	2.000		0%		0%	0	0%
News Alerts							
Number of News Alerts	6		0%		0%	0	0%
Number of Recipients	1.000		0%		0%	0	0%
Open rate	30%		0%		0%	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!
Social Media							
PEDvolution LinkedIn – number of Followers	500		0%		0%	0	0%
PEDvolution LinkedIn – number of Posts	100		0%		0%	0	0%
PEDvolution LinkedIn – Reach	100.000		0%		0%	0	0%
PEDvolution Twitter – number of Followers	1.000		0%		0%	0	0%
PEDvolution Twitter – number of Tweets	100		0%		0%	0	0%
PEDvolution Twitter – Reach	100.000		0%		0%	0	0%
Partners' social media pages – number of posts	100		0%		0%	0	0%
Scientific Publications							
Number of Publications	5	0	0%		0%	0	0%
Number of Journals						0	
Number of Conferences						0	
Popularised Publications (non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed)							
Number of Publications		0				0	
EU or International Level Events							
Number of Events	3		0%		0%	0	0%
Number of Participants/Visitors	200		0%		0%	0	0%
National or Regional Level Events							
Number of Events	5		0%		0%	0	0%
Number of Participants/Visitors	200		0%		0%	0	0%
Final PEDvolution conference (EU-level)							